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**SUPPORTIVE-EDUCATIVE PROGRAM ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF OLDER
ADULT POST-CEREBRAL STROKE SURVIVORS**

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Alana Aissa Gem Barias is a graduate of Bachelor of Science in Nursing in Velez College, Cebu City, Philippines. An experienced nurse who had worked in various fields of nursing including Institute of Neuroscience, Diabetes Care, Emergency Room, Aesthetic Surgery, General Surgery, and Ambulatory Care among others, a Registered Nurse in three countries (Philippines, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and USA) with 17 years under her belt. Her objectives include a lifelong commitment to ongoing education and training in the enhancement of her professional skills and utilization of her knowledge in the best possible way to achieve higher goals and to make a positive impact in the community.

As a former university clinical instructor and a certified diabetes nurse educator, she has always been passionate about sharing information and experiences, and a strong advocate of primary and secondary prevention. She has been inspired by her mentors and UPOU professors to be an active member of society and contributor to the nursing profession. She participated as a volunteer in local and national medical missions of various government and non-government organizations, a Resource Person to several programs and national diabetes care events in other institutions in Metro Manila, and was instrumental in the development of the Department of Health Nurse Certification Program Assessment Rubrics in collaboration with Health Human Resource Development Bureau and multidisciplinary leaders of various government hospitals as a Process Facilitator/Resource Person. A recipient of HERO (Hospital Employee Reaching Out Award) while working in a Magnet hospital, ultimately, she

believes in interdisciplinary approach, patient-centered, exceptional and compassionate nursing care.

She now works in Hematology-Oncology Unit in Metropolitan Hospital in New York, New York USA, where she currently resides with her husband and son. She loves reading books, especially self-help and inspirational, travelling, hiking, and playing the only sport she knows best—badminton.

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According to a famous Chinese proverb “A journey to a thousand miles begins with a single step”. Looking back, the writer is glad to have taken that first step and fortunate to have brought this project into culmination after a long, tortuous journey. It is truly one of her most humbling experiences and all will not be possible without the help of these remarkable people who have provided her their help, love and support through many ways and forms that kept her going till the finish line. Words are not enough to express her gratitude and appreciation to everyone, for this research project was just once a dream but now has become a reality because of each one of you.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	vi
Table of Contents	viii
List of Tables	x
List of Figures	xi
Abstract	xii
CHAPTER I: THE RESEARCH PROBLEM	1
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	3
Significance of the Study	4
Scope of the Study	5
Limitation of the Study	6
CHAPTER II: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	9
Review of Related Literature	9
<i>Quality of Life</i>	9
<i>Supportive Educative Program</i>	15
<i>Stroke</i>	19
<i>Older Adult Stroke Survivors</i>	23
<i>Other Related Literatures</i>	27
Theoretical Framework	30
Conceptual Framework	33
Operational Definition of Terms	35
Hypothesis	38
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	39
Research Design	39
Study Population	40
Sampling Technique	41
Research Setting	42
Data Collection Methods & Procedures	44
Research Instrumentation	49
Data Analysis	50

Qualitative Data	51
Ethical Considerations	52
CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	54
Results and Discussion	54
CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	99
Summary of Findings	99
Conclusions	101
Recommendations	103
REFERENCES	108
APPENDICES	122
Appendix A: Letter of Permission	123
Appendix B: Author's Approval to Use & Translate QOL	127
Appendix C: Research Questionnaires	128
Appendix D: Tagalog WHO-BREF Questionnaire	133
Appendix E: 3-Day Diet and Activity Recall	136
Appendix F: Mini-Mental State Exam	137
Appendix G: The Barthel Index	138
Appendix H: Intervention Protocol	139
Appendix I: Instructional Design	147
Appendix J: Informed Consent Form	153
Appendix K: Research Flow	154
Appendix L: Curriculum Vitae	156

List of Tables

Table 1 Demographic Profile	55
Table 2 Mean Scores of the Physical Domain among Respondents	67
Table 3 Mean Scores of the Psychological Domain among Respondents	68
Table 4 Mean Scores of the Social Domain among Respondents	69
Table 5 Mean Scores of the Environmental Domain among Respondents	69
Table 6 Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Biophysical Profile	79
Table 7 Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Quality of Life	80
Table 8 Themes & Sub-themes of Older Adult Stroke Survivors in Various Facets of Quality of Life	82
Table 9 24-hr Diet and Activity Recall	88

List of Figures

Figure 1 Orem's self-care client-centered theory	32
Figure 2 Conceptual framework	34
Figure 3 Mixed methods explanatory sequential design phases	40
Figure 4 Research protocol	43
Figure 5 Mixed methods explanatory sequential steps	48
Figure 6 Systolic pressure of respondents before & after SEP	59
Figure 7 Diastolic pressure of respondents before & after SEP	60
Figure 8 Heart rate of respondents before & after SEP	62
Figure 9 Weight of respondents before & after SEP	63
Figure 10 Mean arterial pressure of respondents before & after SEP	64
Figure 11 PRE-SEP QOL of respondents in 4 domains	70
Figure 12 POST-SEP QOL of respondents in 4 domains	71
Figure 13 QOL: Physical domain before & after SEP	73
Figure 14 QOL: Psychological domain before & after SEP	75
Figure 15 QOL: Social relationships domain before & after SEP	77
Figure 16 QOL: Environmental domain before & after SEP	78

ABSTRACT

Cerebrovascular stroke incidents are increasing in number, leaving stroke survivors with mental and physical challenges, and often with limited or no understanding to their situation or the therapeutic strategies necessary to live a quality life. This study aims to determine the effects of supportive-educative program (SEP) on the QOL of community-dwelling older adult stroke survivors in selected barangays in Metro Manila, utilizing Dorothea Orem's self-care deficit theory. Specifically, to identify the profile of older adults in terms of biophysical (BP, MAP, Heart Rate, Weight), QOL (Physical, Psychological, Social Relationships, Environment) status and whether there is a significant difference before and after SEP. Mixed methods explanatory sequential design with non-probability purposive sampling was used, employing the questionnaire World Health Organization Quality of Life Brief (WHOQOL-BREF) to gather from 15 respondents. Results showed the mean age of the study population was from the middle-old aged group (70-80), majority of which were male (60 %) married (53.33%), college graduates (53%). Overall data implies that out of 15 respondents there were positive improvements in SBP in 7 out of 15 cases (46.66%), DBP in 5 out of 15 cases (33.33%), MAP in 6 out of 15 cases (40%), with no change in weight, only 8 out of 15 cases (53.33%) had ± 0.206 kilograms difference post-SEP. Social domain is the most constant among the 4 domains of QOL, with a standard deviation of $sd=0.6359$ (mean=3.399) almost identical before and after the program $sd=0.6048$ (mean=3.444) suggesting a constant social QOL among respondents, consistent with the positive personal relationships and social support feedback during the interview with the respondents. Moreover, the respondents have the highest satisfaction (mean=4.133) in their personal relationships

under the social domain. Among the 4 domains, psychological QOL scored the lowest, followed by the environmental, then Physical, with Social domain at the top of the list.

Furthermore, the major themes derived from the focus group discussion were activities of daily living, mobility, and work capacity, with sub themes: awareness in preventive health practices, good compliance in medications, limited activity options, Go foods, home cooked meals, food preparation preference, stroke adaptive functional ability and inability to occupy work. Based on Wilcoxon statistics converted to z-score to test the significance under normal curve, at 0.01% level of significance and two-tailed test, the critical values of z are -1.96 and +1.96, since the obtained value of each z scores did not exceed these values, this study cannot reject the null hypothesis. In conclusion, the SEP has no significant effect on Biophysical Profile of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors and there is no significant difference between the biophysical profile and the QOL of older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors prior and post SEP.

Keywords: cerebrovascular stroke, older-adults, stroke survivors, Quality of Life, WHOQOL-BREF.

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Annually, it is estimated that half a million Filipinos suffer from stroke. Many stroke survivors encounter mental and physical challenges such as difficulty of speech, concentration, memory, weakness, numbness, or stiffness that persist to place the burden on the survivors. The seriousness of post-stroke physical and mental impairments impacts quality of life (Weerd, 2012) Studies indicate that between 61% and 100% of stroke survivors account a decrease in QOL (Grant, 1996; Kelly-Hayes & Paige, 1995; King, 1996; Sisson, 1998; Wyller et al., 1997, cited by Johnson & Pearson, 2012) On the contrary, maintaining adequate engagement in physical activity is a necessity for stroke, stroke survivors, and older adults (Gordon et al. 2004; Jacqui et al., 2012; Mukherjee 2013; Bonomu 2000 cited by Ghassemzadeh et al., 2013) and is necessary to improve function and QOL-related outcomes for older chronic stroke survivors (Stuart et al., 2008) as well as fight against depression which is extremely common condition after stroke (National Stroke Association, 2010) that is said to have an association with lower physical activity levels (Field et al., 2013). In addition, cognitive impairment was said to have a significant effect on activities of daily living (ADL) and self-rated QOL (Barker-Collo et al., 2010; Mitchell et al., 2010).

The lack of information and knowledge is an essential factor for non-compliance to the recommended healthy regimen on stroke survivors. Many older adult survivors leave the hospital before they fully understand and process how the stroke happened,

often having very limited understanding of the therapeutic strategy or its goals. Some have inadequate awareness regarding the underlying conditions that may have caused the stroke. There are times when information is provided during the acute phase of stroke. In some instances, the salient and sensitive information are discussed to them at the time directly following the diagnosis or right before they are discharged from the hospital-when patients find it hard to focus on what is being explained and just wants to go home to their family. For some, despite the benefits of health maintenance activities such as adequate engagement in physical activity, proper diet, and stress management, only a few are compliant to the recommendations. It is assumed that stroke specific supportive-educative interventions help ensure accurate understanding and promote adherence and compliance for stroke survivors which directly and indirectly improve QOL post-stroke. However, in a study composed of community dwelling recruited via disability support groups, information about what to do ranked 4th in barriers to exercise behavior behind impairment, money, and accessible facilities (Kinne et al., 1999).

Working in the neuroscience department had increased the investigator's awareness of the gap between hospital care and continuity of care in the community, specifically in the maintenance stage. It has been observed that stroke survivor's need for self-management information is often overlooked, such as the knowledge of the disease and the necessary skills and attitude for healing, recovery, and for secondary prevention. In effect, the capacities of stroke survivors are undermined and their potential to live life to the fullest is downgraded. They are often pre-conditioned to be dependent on others even when deemed competent. Promotion of adequacy of self-care agency specifically tailored to their needs as well as their limitations is therefore warranted to empower stroke survivors. The rising incidence of stroke inside and

outside the investigator's social circle and the growing demand on lifestyle modification has been a motivating factor in pursuing the study.

It is the objective of this research to know the quality of life (QOL) of post-stroke older patients and whether a supportive-educative program (independent variable) will improve it (QOL-dependent variable). Employing self-care deficit theory of Dorothea Orem, the study is directed towards conducting a supportive-educative program that caters to the needs of stroke survivors. This according to the assumption that health promotion activities improve QOL and the premise that human beings are responsible for their self-care in relation to their health. Utilizing the World Health Organization's QOL questionnaire (WHOQOL-BREF) this study aims to improve the stroke survivor's quality of life. Thus, this study aspires to know their QOL before and after the program, and whether there is a significant difference before and after the program's implementation.

Statement of the Problem

This research study aims to determine the effects of supportive-educative program (SEP) to the QOL of older stroke survivors. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the profile of older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors before and after the SEP in terms of:

1.1 Biophysical

1.1.1 BP

1.1.2 MAP (mean arterial pressure)

1.1.3 Heart rate

1.1.4 Weight

1.2 Quality of life

1.2.1 Physical

1.2.2 Psychological

1.2.3 Social Relationships

1.2.4 Environment

2. Is there a significant difference between the biophysical profile and the QOL of older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors?

2.1 Before SEP

2.2 After SEP

3. Is there a significant relationship between the stroke survivors' profile and their QOL in terms of:

a. Age

b. Sex

c. Civil Status

d. Educational Status

Significance of the Study

Patient and Family - The findings of this study will help post stroke patients gain awareness and understanding on the importance of secondary prevention of stroke and lifestyle modification through health promotive activities. Health promotion being a process that incorporates not only measures to strengthen skills and capabilities but also those that impact public and individual health by changing social, environmental, and economic status.

Nurse - This study will provide an evidence-based practice to the nurse's role in secondary prevention and health promotion initiatives through supportive-educative

programs. The focus of QOL in stroke survivors in the community maintains the nurse's vital role in public health. If deemed to significantly improve the QOL of stroke survivors, the investigator hopes to implement the Supportive-Educative Program in the hospital's rehabilitation centers and possibly in barangay health centers that need supportive-educative programs to help assist community post-stroke survivors.

Nursing practice - The extent of nursing's responsibility in promoting QOL is extensive, and this study includes developing practices and processes and test interventions to promote it in stroke survivors. The information derived from this study may be used to improve the quality of life of stroke survivors post hospitalization, those with disability, and health conditions that need secondary prevention. The utilization of Dorothea Orem's concept in this study may be used to pattern health promotion programs for other chronic illnesses that need self-care and continuity of care.

Research - This study will help encourage nurses to participate and undertake research for marginalized populations such as the post-stroke survivors and adults with disability. To not only focus in the acute, convalescent, or recovery phase but also in the secondary prevention which is usually more serious if not fatal. This research will contribute to the wide body of knowledge aimed for secondary prevention and self-care management in stroke related investigations in the hope of improving their QOL, as well as in strengthening healthcare services of stroke survivors.

Scope of the Study

The supportive-educative program was designed only for older adults previously diagnosed with stroke for more than a year and have finished formal physical rehabilitation. To create a more homogenous group, older adults aging 60 years old and above was selected. This includes patients who were able to participate

and understand simple instructions and are functionally independent based on Barthel's Index. However, it excludes those who were confined in the hospital, bedbound, currently sick, and unable to follow simple instructions.

Respondents with comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, diabetes) will be included because aside from the greater possibility of having more than one chronic condition in this age bracket than any other group, regular exercise for health maintenance is potentially beneficial for secondary prevention for them, given that the activities in the program are not contraindicated to their condition. Medical consent from the physician or physical therapist was secured and consent from the participants prior to the study was obtained to ensure that they are physiologically capable of performing specific activities related to study.

This study focuses on assessing the four domains of quality of life of the respondents, namely physical, psychological, environmental, and social, along with their biophysiological profile and does not cover other medical aspects nor any other comorbidities of older adult stroke survivors.

Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations making it impossible for the researcher to establish a relationship between stroke patient characteristics.

First, there was a limited quantity of participants qualified for the study. Out of the initial 39 program participants gathered from Barangay 272, Zone 25, Barangay Sta. Ana, Office of the Senior Citizen, and Manila Medical Center Rehabilitation and Diabetes Care Center, only 17 respondents qualified for SEP and only 15 successfully finished the one-month long program. Gathering respondents in the barangay level limits the number of respondents to the officially registered senior citizens in the

neighborhood and excludes those living in transient and non-active residents of the community. Challenges encountered include finding the eligible respondents that are willing to participate and will fit the time frame. Unfortunately, some respondents that were willing do not qualify the criteria.

Second, the method used to gather respondents is quite limiting. The utilization of posters, flyers, telephone call and text messaging deemed unsatisfactory to reach potential respondents. Snowballing and recruitment through face-to-face and solicitation was insufficient and regarded inefficient in collecting respondents.

The Hawthorne effect may have portrayed a part in the result of the study with the study being conducted in the Hospital setting and with other respondents. Environment impacts the behavior, mood and motivation of people and peers may directly and indirectly affect the way people think in a group through shared experiences and ideas. A double-blind experiment may be a better option however, a more challenging approach.

Another limitation is the geographic location of the older adult population. Due to safety compliance and budget, it was not deemed safe and practical to recruit populations that are too far from the program location, or the city of Manila. Thus, the sample may not represent respondents from other parts of Metro Manila such as Quezon city, Makati, Marikina among others. The economic environment of the study area altogether further limits the potential to generalize findings, with participants coming from District I, II, III, V, and VI of the cities.

In addition, physical limitations of older adult stroke survivors greatly affected the number of eligible participants. The less physically able and inactive post-cerebrovascular older adults are not able to participate. Surviving patients with aphasia are also deemed ineligible because of communication issues that may affect

the validity of data. The lack of caregiver support may have also discouraged participation for a number of reasons such as transport safety or inability to write on the questionnaires among others.

Included in the drawbacks of this investigation is the limitation of time and extent of exercise, as older adults are prone to physical and mental fatigue. Setting these limits is important to avoid fatigue in the participants. Excessive tiredness, typically resulting from mental or physical exertion or illness was avoided. The study was employed in a span of one month in a one-hour intervention conducted thrice a week for a total of 10 sessions. The physical exercise incorporated was a low- to moderate-intensity, isometric exercise. A high intensity exercise was not utilized in the investigation for safety precaution. Also, the physical structure of the setting may influence the participation's behavior, comfort, and cooperation. Thus, a comfortable atmosphere with a good sound system and visual aids is imperative.

Lastly, attrition is another significant limitation of the study. This is relatively common to this type of research and is evident to other similar studies conducted. The various reasons are numerous, but the majority is due to the nature of the disease and the accompanying health complications involved. Therefore, the data available may not be generalizable to the post-stroke older adult population. Weaknesses of the study include lack of homogenous respondents, unsatisfactory recruitment method, constraints of qualified respondents, possible Hawthorne effect, contained geographic location and limited resources, and attrition. One of the strengths of this study, however, is that it reflects the point of view of the participants and provides a subjective information of their experience quantitatively and qualitatively. Since QOL is a subjective phenomenon, gathering the perspectives of the respondents and facilitators captures a unique viewpoint of their QOL and stroke experience.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This chapter contains discussions of concepts related to the independent variable and dependent variable of this study. Concepts related to the former will be discussed first followed by the latter.

Quality of Life

The standards of quality of life (QOL) in relation to the concept of a person's health is quite complex and may vary for everyone, culture, and health condition. Since 1970's and for the earlier century social scientists started studying QOL, which then was recognized as material well-being and money. In the later century, a shift transpired in perception of life and values to happiness. There are different concepts of QOL in different fields: Sociology describes QOL as based on opinion, sense of well-being, considering individual needs and understanding (Ferris, 2004). Economics view it as the standard of living (Stroup, 2007), while in Medicine it is the ratio of health and illness with the factors influencing healthy lifestyle (Dimenäs et al., 1990). The World Health Organization defined quality of life as "an individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns" (WHO, cited by Mukherjee, 2013). Health being the state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity (WHO, 1946; 2006, cited by Green et al., 2010).

Dennis Raphael (2010) mentioned four overlapping reasons of why health promoters and rehabilitation workers focus on the issues of their life and its quality.

This is because 1) Quality of life may be determinant of the form that aging takes for a particular individual, 2) improved quality of life may be a desired goal of health promotion activities, 3) quality of life can serve as an indicator of needs, and d) quality of life provides a focus for the role of environments within health promotion and rehabilitation. Furthermore, QOL is a concept that encompasses a wide range of experiences of the human population, which is one of the many measures that shapes the essentials and health challenges of the elderly population and their advancement (Bonomu, 2000 cited by Ghassemzadeh et al., 2013).

There are multiple aspects and concepts to consider in measuring QOL in older adults: functional ability, socioeconomic status, emotional state, intellectual activity, cultural and ethical values, religiosity, health, living environment, and daily activities (Vagetti et al. 2014) among many others. One of the main reasons the older adult's daily activities are affected is due to disability caused by stroke, which is a leading cause of incapacity, predisposing stroke survivors to a sedentary lifestyle, especially after rehabilitation (Lofgren, 1999, cited by Morris et al., 2011). The consequences of stroke are classified into problems in the "body structure and function dimension" and in the "activity and participation dimension" (WHO, cited by Gordon 2004). The structure of the human body and its function are inevitably affected, and the stroke effects are usually "impairments" such as hemiplegia, spasticity, and aphasia are the primary neurological disorders that are caused by stroke. While "disabilities" pertain to diminished capacity to perform functions of daily living such as dressing, bathing, or walking, this can also be classified into different magnitudes, which are also referred to as "activity limitations". According to WHO, older adult's regular involvement in physical activity plays an important part in healthy aging and in the promotion of good QOL. Caspersen (1985 cited by Field, 2013) defined physical activity as any bodily

movement produced by skeletal muscle that result in energy expenditure above a basal level.

Physical activity was positively and consistently associated with some QOL domain among older individuals according to a systematic review on QOL by Vagetti et al. (2014) where its physical movement was investigated in older adults. In another study which pursued the influence of frequency of physical activity using the Human Activity Profiles and WHOQOL-BREF as a tool, concluded that a greater weekly frequency of physical activity was associated with higher values in the physical domain of QOL (Alexander et al. 2009, Grimmett et al. 2011). It was discovered that at least five physical activity sessions per week was related to higher scores in several QOL domains such as global QOL, physical, functional, and social domains on colorectal cancer survivor patients. According to an investigation by Brown et al. (2004) that centered on the regularity of activity, patients who performed moderate physical activity with low weekly frequency (1 or 2 days) resulted to a 30% greater chance of experiencing more than two weeks of unhealthy days versus those who performed almost a week of moderate physical activity.

However, despite the advantages of physical activity to the QOL of older adults, quantitative studies on stroke survivors showed evidence of low physical activities of stroke survivors. In a survey conducted (n=312; mean age=63) by Shaughnessy et al. (2006) results show that only 31% exercised four times a week, while 32% had stopped physical activity since their stroke. Another study by Mohan et al. (2009) mentioned that it was frequently cited that the widespread unmet clinical need people experience post stroke is reduced mobility. Hence, providing opportunities for stroke patients to engage in health promotion activities by making stroke related programs available can encourage movement that can help impact their well-being appears to

be necessity than just an option. This is supported by studies showing how exercise schemes conducted in communities proved to help improve quality of life in stroke survivors (Reed et al., 2010; Yoo et al., 2011; Sharma et al, 2012). Interventions designed to educate stroke survivors regarding strengthening behaviors that encourage exercise utilizing self-efficacy and outcome expectations such as reminders from doctors may influence individuals in performing physical activity (Shaughnessy et al., 2006).

A meta-analysis and systematic review by Field et al. (2013) on physical activity after stroke observed that stroke survivors, both ambulatory and non-ambulatory do not achieve recommended levels of activity. Risk modelling studies have indicated that physical activity is a factor that improves chances of preventing another stroke. The study recommends identifying ways to promote physical activity amongst ambulatory stroke survivors, and ways to reduce disability so that stroke survivors can participate in levels of physical activity that are likely to have an effect on secondary stroke. However, there has been a wide variation across multiple samples, and the interventions or surveillance as well as the instruments used to quantify the dependent variable is numerous, making it difficult to find a consistent association of these factors.

Psychological and social are the other essential factors that was investigated by Morris et al. (2012), who probed these factors in post stroke patients through a structured literature review of previous studies on disabilities, stroke, and physical activity. It was discovered that there are pertinent influences on a person's behavior towards physical activity post-stroke such as their self-efficacy, beliefs, and social support and for these to be included in theoretically based physical interventions may prove beneficial. Additionally, Socio-demographic factors such as ethnicity, gender, education, income, and age, may also be instrumental in determining likely

commitment to physical activity (Tost et al., 2001) degree of assistance, range of activities, and factors in the society and community that influence QOL (Newsom 1996; Raphael et al. 2010; Mukherjee 2013) Other factors such as the place where the patient live, the support he/she gets from people, post-stroke depression and the level of activity also plays a role in the quality of life of older adults. In a survey of Rimmer et al. (2008) to adults with an average age of 54.2 years old with unilateral stroke (n=83) it was revealed that there are five perceived barriers to exercise that are common which further reduce the participation of post-stroke patients. The first one is usually the cost of the exercise program (61%), followed by the lack of awareness of a fitness center in the area (57%), no means of transportation to a fitness center (57%), no knowledge of how (46%) and where to exercise (44%). The least common barriers were the lack of interest (16%), the lack of time (11%) and concern that exercise would worsen their condition (1%).

Jasper Fellowship Monograph (1999, series 7) conducted a 12 -month exploratory study on 50-59 and 60 years old above stroke survivors and their caregivers (N=100) to help in the identification of their condition prior and following stroke as well as recognizing the resources that can be useful to them. Findings show that family members are primary providers of care (50%), basic needs of patients are well provided on the first visit, however there is a decreasing or limited financial resource on the second visit. In addition, housing arrangements are a factor that affects comfort and safety while on the road to recovery. Recommendations from this one year-study include tapping or linking with community health centers and establishing consistent and regularly scheduled information and health promotion education campaigns and disability prevention.

Local qualitative studies show how psychosocial factors in the Filipino population

affect older adults. In a sociology study of Bonifacio (1983-1988) on 75-80 years old (N=50) men and women using exploratory, clustered cohort sampling scheme using structured interview, leisurely familial causerie, reminiscence, and behavioral observations documented Filipino's concept of health and illness in the "Malas suerte" phenomenon. Interestingly, this is the Filipino's concept of health-a fortune. When one is healthy, he is supposed to be fortunate because health is "suerte" meaning good fortune. Inversely, when one is ill, he is considered to have bad luck since illness is equated with "malas", meaning misfortune. A fatalistic attitude or "*bahala na*" (alluding all events that fall in his life to "*Bathala*") is a Filipino attitude, which is negative when a person no longer seeks other alternatives to come out of the situation. Another sociology investigation by Lavares (2011) who conducted qualitative-quantitative study on older Filipinos by focused group discussion revealed that the most valuable coping resource is religion. The study described numerous pathways linking religion and life satisfaction among older people such as a sense of meaning which allows them to manage life's challenges and allows them to accept problems with a sense of value. Religion also provides social support through friends from their religious congregation, while to some, it serves as a guide in decision making, or provides opportunities to be active after retirement by giving them new roles to fill. In addition, religion is said to help lessen their fears of death through belief in the afterlife. Results of the study show that faith, spirituality, or religiosity is one of the primary sources of life satisfaction for women, although this is not found to be true for men. In contrary to the negative fatalistic view of "*bahala na ang Diyos*" attitude, the study gives the older adults a source of hope and strength to help accept their problems and serves as a psychological support. This holistic approach should empower individuals and communities to take actions for their own health, foster leadership for public health,

promote intersectoral action to build healthy public policies and create sustainable health systems in the society. These elements capture the essence of “health promotion”, which is about enabling people to take control over their health and its determinants, and thereby improve their health. It includes interventions at the personal, organizational, social, and political levels to facilitate adaptations (lifestyle, environmental, etc.) conducive to improving or protecting health.

Supportive Educative Program

The essence of health promotion is enabling people to gain control over their health and its determinants through personal, organization, social, and political interventions to facilitate lifestyle adaptations among others to improving health WHO 2009). Supportive Educative Programs therefore moves beyond a focus on individual behavior towards a wide range of social and environmental interventions that includes positive wellbeing, acknowledging the multidimensional and holistic nature of health. There are two types of health promotion in stroke as recommended by the Stroke Society of the Philippines: primary stroke prevention and secondary stroke prevention (Duncan et al. 2005 cited in Stroke Society of the Philippines) In the former, the key is therapeutic lifestyle changes such as quitting smoking, managing weight, regular exercise and satisfactory BP control as well as the management and treatment of predisposing factors such as diet modification for patients with diabetes or cardiovascular conditions. While the latter includes lifestyle modification, dietary guidelines, and medication recommendations based on NCEP III guidelines (National Cholesterol Education Program III guidelines).

Nola Pender’s health promotion model defines a person as embodying a unique set of characteristics and experiences which affect every person’s actions. The

behavior motivated by the desire to enhance well-being and realize the full health potential of human is what health promotion stands for. The major concepts of this model are behavior-specific cognitions/affect and behavioral outcomes which involves concepts of protecting health or preventing illness. People in all their biopsychosocial intricacy intermingle with the environment, progressively transforming the environment and being transformed as time goes by. It is assumed that individuals actively regulate their behavior and healthcare professionals have the capacity to influence individuals through entering the interpersonal environment. This study uses the health promotion model in the intervention program for stroke survivors.

Johnson & Pearson (2012) conducted a qualitative study in community dwelling stroke survivors (N=41) wherein participants were assigned to a treatment and control group for a 2-hour structured educational class for a four-week period. The study showed that adaptation of stroke survivors was observed when they returned to living in the community was facilitated by the supportive educative strategies taught. This supports the idea of SEP in helping stroke survivors adjust to the community once they are equipped with the right knowledge and skills. Another study showed a positive impact to a group of post-stroke participants through a 3-month clinic intervention. In a RCT study by Green et al. (2007) where (N=200) participants were assigned to an education-counselling interview and completed a stroke knowledge questionnaire at baseline, post-appointment, and three months post appointment in an ambulatory care setting shows a statistically significant difference in stroke knowledge ($p < 0.001$) from the 1st month compared to the 3rd month as well as a significant shift from a passive to active stage of change for the overall sample ($p < 0.000$). The researchers concluded that utilizing motivational interviewing and a stage of change model can improve knowledge and initiate change no matter how limited the contact is with the patients.

In another study, utilizing a time a quasi-experimental study also employing a three-point data collection: baseline, after a week, and three months after the intervention by Sit et al. (2007), determined the effect of a community-based stroke prevention program (eight sessions for 2 hours) in 147 minor strokes (77=intervention; 70= control group). The study yet again discovered noteworthy optimistic changes in terms of the knowledge of stroke warning signs ($p<0.001$); treatment seeking response in case of a stroke ($p<0.001$), medical compliance ($p<0.001$); self-blood pressure monitoring ($p<0.001$) as well as lifestyle modification of dietary habits (reduction in salt food intake, $p=0.004$), except in walking exercise participation where no significant improvement was found. Nevertheless, the study concluded that there is a sustained effect of positive changes in knowledge and skills in participants overall. The author mentioned that effective educational intervention of nurses helped clients integrate their learned knowledge and skills into their real-life practice in terms of expanding knowledge about stroke, enhancing self-health monitoring practice, and sustaining behavioral changes when adopting a healthy lifestyle for stroke prevention. An affirmation that patient education has shifted further than teaching people facts, empowering them in their daily self-care management.

Prevention is arguably the most readily applicable and affordable part of our knowledge, yet it is often neglected according to Stroke Society of the Philippines 2006. Knowing what to do and having the proper attitude in self-care management can help stroke survivors deal with post stroke disabilities and save expenses by preventing another episode of stroke. The National Stroke Society (2013) promotes the necessity of “healthy environments to support healthy habits and lifestyle” and to discover as much as possible about stroke survivors and their recovery, including the many ways to reestablish independence. A study by Anon 1997 and Roberson 1992

(cited by Vermeire et al., 2001) revealed there is a correlation between compliance and the understanding, beliefs, and encounters of the patient and the members of their family and friends. Health professionals being a provider of information necessary for the healing and treatment of the patient place a great priority in compliance, but for the person affected with stroke, there are other matters that are considered more of their priority such as controlling symptoms, averting medical crises, retaining financial comfort, or appreciating a quality lifestyle. This is further attested in a study specifying compliance as determined by the knowledge and attitudes of the patient (McGavock 1996 cited in Vermeire et al., 2001) where patients do not view all recommended treatments as necessary for their best interests (Roberson MHB, 1992). This results to non-compliance to the health management being taught to them. Non-compliance which is defined as the “non-adherence to a therapeutic recommendation following an informed decision and expressed intention to attain therapeutic goals” (NANDA 1995, cited by Russel et al., 2002) is one of the challenges faced by healthcare as patients seem to establish their own systems of self-management that they believe best suits their lifestyles, belief patterns, and personal priorities. This is consistent with Albert Bandura’s self-efficacy theory where he states that people’s self-beliefs of efficacy determine how much effort they will exert in an endeavor and how long they will persevere in the face of obstacles (Bandura 1988; Bandura et al., 2000). In a survey (N=750 adults) conducted by Roxas (2009) on public awareness about stroke called Stroke Awareness Gap in the Philippines (SAGIP) in Currimao, Ilocos Norte, the results show that the public’s knowledge on risk factors of stroke is generally poor. Only 34.4% of the respondents showed correct knowledge of what stroke is, while 20.5% confused it with heart attack and 27.2% admitted they do not know what stroke is. This information could possibly impact how people protect themselves from

predisposing factors of stroke and how effectively they can adjust their lifestyle accordingly through increased knowledge on the risk factors and prevention of stroke.

Stroke and heart disease is similar and are both common lifestyle diseases which can be prevented through health education. In a qualitative study on individuals with high cardiovascular risk, Murray et al. (2013) sought to clarify apparent aspects thought to affect preservation of changed healthy lifestyle. The patient's commitment to adhere to recommended medications and assume key healthy lifestyle behaviors were looked into avoiding smoking, eating a balanced diet, limiting alcohol consumption and keeping active and five components influencing maintenance known to predict uptake of lifestyle behavior change: beliefs, knowledge transport and other costs, emotions, and friends and family support. The results showed formal and informal social support, personal beliefs, knowledge on the causes and management of poor health, and the value of maintaining lifestyle behaviors, as well as psychological factors that includes attitude, thinking and coping styles, problem solving skills are the most frequently reported influence. The key themes based on the thorough analysis of interrelationships between factors within categories were social support, education and knowledge, and beliefs and emotions. The study concludes that addressing barriers and facilitators within support programs are important for maintaining healthy behaviors would be of value in the long-term.

Stroke

A stroke otherwise called "brain attack" happens when a blood clot blocks an artery or a blood vessel breaks, disrupting blood flow to an area of the brain, resulting to dead brain cells or brain damage. The abilities dictated by the area of the brain are lost when brain cells die during a stroke, such as communication, movement, and

recollection (National Stroke Association, 2014).

Stroke is essentially categorized under the diseases of the vascular system and is said to be the second most common cause of death worldwide and in the Philippines, according to the National Stroke Association (2014), predicted to cause 6.5 million deaths in 2015 and 7.8 million in 2030, and is considered the leading cause of permanent disability in adults with up to 32% of all stroke survivors (The Stroke Society of the Philippines, 2006). The WHO's (World Health Organization) Global Burden of Stroke (2005) reported 14 per 1,000 people prevalent of stroke in the Philippines, more than the average of <5 per 1,000 in the industrialized world.

Diabetes mellitus was known to be the number one risk factor (89%) of stroke, followed by hypertension (80%), atrial fibrillation (78%), previous stroke (77%), and heart failure and/or ischemic heart disease (66%) according to a study of n-195 (Sooman et al., 2015). The effects of stroke to the patient depends on where the stroke occurs in the brain and how much the brain is damaged. A small stroke could affect only minor problems such as weakness of an arm or a leg, while people who have larger strokes may be paralyzed on one side or lose their ability to speak. While some people recover completely from strokes, there are more than 2/3 of survivors will have some type of disability (National Stroke Association, 2014). Therefore, the decision for rehabilitation is based on several factors: type and severity of neurologic deficits, cognitive status, physical endurance, and preferences of patient and family (Kelly-Hayes et al., 1995). Hemiplegia, spasticity, and aphasia which are major neurological disorders of stroke causes decreased capacity to execute daily functions, such as getting dressed, taking a bath, or ambulating, and is described in an Indian Journal of Gerontology "hampers social adjustment and features among the most important determinants of diminution in quality of life" (Mukherjee, 2013).

According to the International Classification of Functioning (ICF) disability is a blanket term for movement restrictions, impairments, and involvement limits that signifies the undesirable aspects of the interaction between the health condition(s) and that of the individual's environmental and personal factors. On the other hand, functioning pertains to body function, structures, activities and participation that represents the constructive or neutral aspects of the interaction between a person's health condition(s) and that individual factor (environment and personal factors) (WHO ,2001). Impairments such as hemiplegia, spasticity, and aphasia, are the chief neurological disorders resulting from stroke. Disabilities are activity limitations manifested by decreased capacity to accomplish daily functions, such as dressing, bathing, or walking (Gordon et al., 2004). The extent of activity limitation is commonly correlated to but not completely dependent on the degree of body impairment (Roth et al., 1998, cited in Gordon et al., 2004).

Functional independence is one of the important indicators of a stroke patient's readiness to be discharged from the hospital in addition to their current level of independence. Physical disability of any kind prevents normal function in instrumental activities of daily living (IADLs) and activities of daily living (ADLs) by hampering social adjustment and features, which is further discussed in an Indian Journal of Gerontology as among the most important determinants of diminution in quality of life (Mukherjee, 2013). A tool recommended by the Stroke Association, Barthel's index, measures activities indicating functional capacity that include feeding, bathing, grooming, dressing, elimination capacity, and mobility. This is easily measured by asking the patient or the patient's caregiver or through direct observation. Assessing the person's functional activity is significant as it is an indicator of their ability to perform exercise. Exercise is an important component for lifestyle modification change.

Moreover, having a baseline functional capacity score helps design a more apt physical fitness program made for their special needs. Post-stroke participants may be classified as dependent, partially dependent, or fully independent. Although, some patients are discharged without any limiting symptom, some are half paralyzed, and some may have very minimal disability. McKevitt et al, (2010) needs assessment survey results showed that about two thirds of stroke survivors are estimated to have residual neurologic deficits and approximately half are left with disabilities. Furthermore, reduced mobility directly or indirectly affects their quality of life. An increase in the limitations of the activities in daily life is directly associated with the increase of comorbidities on the aged thus, decreasing their QOL (Calasans et al., 2004, cited by Alencar et al.2009). Alencar et al. (2009) argued that although benefits of physical activity practice are widely published, few are the ones that do such activities regularly, especially in the aged subgroup. Eliopoulos (2009) reiterated that although the patients may perform tasks awkwardly and slowly, family members need to recognize that permitting independent function is physically and psychologically more advantageous for the stroke survivors compared to performing tasks for them (Gerontological Nursing, 2005). Stroke is a lifestyle disease. Some would think that it is a “rich people’s disease”, but in reality, it is a disease that does not recognize social status. The lifestyle of a person, however, may be a risk factor to stroke.

Lifestyle modification in addition to compliance of medication for specific diseases (e.g., hypertension, diabetes, cholesterol) is imperative for primary and secondary prevention of stroke. After a patient had stroke regardless of social status, he/she is more prone to having a stroke in the next 5-10 years. A guideline for managing life at home after stroke was created by the Stroke Society of the Philippines, a private organization composed of stroke experts, have included

secondary prevention wherein a nurse plays an important part through public education, and active participation in health promotion programs involving lifestyle modification. According to Stroke Society of the Philippines (2010) enabling a person to be cognizant of his risk of developing (MI or) stroke within 5- or 10-years' time may promote addressing associated risks and introduce suitable healthy lifestyle modifications. However, there is very little follow through for stroke survivors and fewer lifestyle change activities to empower them and help them live a quality life.

The two leading common health condition, overweight and obesity, are correlated with progressively increasing risk of ischemic stroke (Strazzullo et al., 2010). Excess weight is usually a result of unhealthy eating or overeating. Eating occurs in response to hunger stimuli but excessive eating causes overweight and obesity. The Mayer's glucostatic theory describes how low circulating blood glucose (CHO) triggers hunger while Flatt's glycogen static theory explains how low CHO stores liver and muscle glycogen triggers hunger (Blundel et al., 2013). To control weight, it is important to control a person's eating habits and choice of diet in addition to regular exercise.

Older Adult Stroke Survivors

Age is a risk factor and a crucial variable in the outcome of stroke survivors. Age can be classified chronologically, the number of years a person has lived, or biologically, an individual's development based on biomarkers, (Kowalczyk D, 2015) psychological age, a more subjective description of one's experience and functional age, with a combination of chronological, biological, and psychological age. The United Nations (UN) classified older adults as those 60 years and above, this being the starting point for old age (Ghassemzadeh 2012). As human life is extended, there

is an increasing figure of illnesses (Campbell et al., 1994, cited by Brajkovic, 2009) that make satisfactory functioning more challenging. This is shown in study that patients under 65 had better outcomes than those over 65 years (N=154) as the younger patients recovered better than older than 65 years old (Feigenson, 1977; Lehmann 1975; cited by Kotila 1984). Almost three-quarters of all strokes occur in people over the age of 65 and the risk of having a stroke more than doubles each decade after the age of 55 (National Stroke Association, 2001) Although, Bjorn-Mortensen et al (2013) have concluded in their study that incidence rates were also high in the younger age groups (N=156) with no significant difference in gender at the time of diagnosis. In terms of gender differences, Focht et al (2014) in their study in stroke recognition among stroke survivors, concluded that women are significantly older than men (N=71) at the time of stroke (62 years old vs. 55 years old: $p < .05$) which implies that women tend to have stroke later in life.

Cognition, communication, and prospects for engagement in the community are some of the conditions that affect stroke survivors in addition to mobility. Personality changes are one example, which often accompany neurologic problems in stroke survivors. Another common effect of stroke is depression. This may be the effect of the area affected by the stroke or the resulting limitations of functions that lowers their mood. Depression, according to several studies, is the most repeatedly described as the behavioral outcome of stroke (Robinson et al., 1987; Sinyor et al., 1986; Wade, Parker & Hewer, 1986, cited by Sisson 1998) 34%-40% have reportedly developed major or minor depression scores after 24 months based in a longitudinal study of Robinson (1987). Activity restrictions due to multiple condition is also one of the common experiences by individuals with stroke, especially with increased age (Morris et al, 2013.) Furthermore, Eliopoulos (2005) added that patients may become

depressed as they realize their limitations or become frustrated by their need to be dependent on others. Family members may need help in understanding the reasons for this behavior and in learning effective ways of dealing with it. Most importantly, encouraging them that understanding, patience and tolerance are needed in taking care of post-stroke patients. Also, qualitative studies (N=16) of post-stroke reported altered spousal relationships in terms of sexuality, sexual desire, and functioning (N=16) loss of sense of control, relationship adjustments (N=8) which have a substantial influence on post-stroke quality of life mostly in the long term (Thompson & Ryan, 2009; Coombs 2007).

Hypertension is a major risk factor of stroke and happens to be widespread in older adults as stroke occurs double to more than double in elderly hypertensive people than in age-matched normotensive subjects (SHEP, 1991 cited by Porth, 2006). The stroke risk in people with high blood pressure occurs over an eightfold range, depending on the quantity of accompanying risk factors (Kannel, 1996 cited by Porth, 2006) This is also proven in a cohort longitudinal study called Framingham Study (N=5000) which studied the characteristics of 30-59 years old where they found hypertension as a risk factor of stroke (Framingham Heart Study, 2001) In one study conducted by Brajkovic et al. (2009) in older adults (N=60) who are stroke survivors 93% have high blood pressure. In another study of Kotila et al. (1984) (N=154) 45% had comorbid hypertension and 65% had elevated blood pressure at the acute stage. In addition, the collective effects of smoking, high cholesterol, obesity, and low physical activity increase the probability of atherosclerosis (Framingham Heart Study, 2001) which is a risk factor in stroke. Allowing a patient to have the knowledge of his risk of developing MI or stroke in the next 5 or 10 years may inspire him to address recognized risks and begin appropriate positive changes towards healthy lifestyle

(Stroke Society of the Philippines, 2010). In the Philippines, there is yet a database that shows an exact amount of prevalence of hypertension in older adults, and stroke incidence data for stroke is yet to be available.

Physical activity is one of the many ways of building a healthy lifestyle that is likely to reduce stroke or repeated incidence of stroke as suggested by risk modelling studies (Hackam et al., 2007). The American Heart Association (AHA) proposes 20minutes to an hour of medium to high intensity exercise (expressed as 40-70% of either peak oxygen uptake or heart rate reserve) in 3-7 days in a week for stroke survivors (Gordon et al., 2004). However, a meta-analysis and systematic review of physical activity after stroke by Field et al. (2013) found out that post-stroke patients do not achieve the recommended levels of activity, even those who are ambulatory. In addition, Saunders et al., (2013) also indicated that levels of physical fitness are low after stroke. Despite the importance of physical activity in stroke survivors, according to West et al. (2012) the extent of physical activity performed after stroke has only been evaluated in an inpatient environment. The reason for this may be to manage risks in implementing high intensity exercises specifically for post stroke older adult patients.

Role discontinuity is a term used to describe the disruption of position appreciated or role executed due to an accident, such as a stroke incident, emergency, and change of position or retirement, of which are considered determining factors of positive perception of older adults, according to Letty Kuan (1993) such as health status, income, work status, family constellation, self-preparation. Maintaining proper care of the mind and body at any age is deemed important in maintaining health in older adults. Family performs an essential role not only in emotional support but in financial support as well, especially to those who have stopped working or earning

money. The economic level (classified as poor, moderate or rich) may signify living conditions or nutritional status. In addition, self-preparation which includes developing a positive attitude towards aging while still young contributes a great deal to feeling comfortable while growing old (Kuan, 1993).

Other Related Literature

The Philippine Constitution incorporated a thorough approach to the improvement of health, placing priority on the needs of the disadvantaged, ill, older adults, incapacitated, women and children (Article XIII, Section 11). This is also stated in the Expanded Senior Citizens Act or RA 9994 which supports the objective of giving full support to the development of the total well-being of older adults and to deliver a broad health care and rehabilitation approach for disabled senior citizens to promote their capability to attain a more significant and productive aging” (Expanded Senior Citizens Act, 2010). Maintaining and promoting wellness is central to the idea of Orem’s theory in the sense that the nursing agency provides the support older persons needs to promote the continuation of life, self-preservation, personal health, and well-being (Maty Fraser, 1996).

The Health Belief Model pioneered by Hochbaum, (1958) and modified by Becker (1974) suggests that a person’s decision whether to change behavior will be influenced by an evaluation of its feasibility based on their perceived seriousness, perceived susceptibility and its benefits weighed against its costs or barriers. This model is frequently applied in health instruction and health advancement (Glanz et al., 2002). This model explains that precautionary health behaviors which includes health promoting (e.g., diet, exercise, compliance in medication) and health-risk behaviors (e.g., smoking, unhealthy food choices, sedentary lifestyle) modified by factors (e.g.,

age, sex, education status) perceived threat (stroke recurrence) and cues to action (stroke incident) play a role in behavioral change. This will depend relatively on the stroke survivor's perception and personal health beliefs which he/she acquired before, during, or after the stroke event, previous experiences in life, and knowledge learned in formal and informal education.

Albert Bandura defined self-efficacy as confidence in "one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to manage prospective situations" and defined these principles as determining factor of people's thinking, behavior, and feelings (Bandura, 1994 cited by Cherry, Psychology Expert). The self-efficacy theory provides an underpinning of how a person behaves and what makes a person chose a specific behavior. In a health promotion such as an exercise program, self-efficacy is imperative in making a choice, changing behavior, and maintaining a routine (Bandura, 1988). Experience, modelling, coaching, providing feedback, and emotional status of a stroke survivor all plays a part in a person's self-efficacy judgement. Self-efficacy influences their decision making; the amount of effort they will put forth in what they do; their perseverance in the face of obstacles and setbacks; and whether their thought patterns are self-deterring or self-supporting the extent of stress and depression people encounter in coping with environmental challenges (Bandura, 1988). In relation to this study, the investigator aims to improve the stroke survivor's self-efficacy through increasing the self-care supply of the person (knowledge, skills, and attitude).

The social cognitive theory of Bandura's self-efficacy theory is integrated in the Transtheoretical Model suggesting scientific and professional shifts of health promotion programs. The shifts include the change of paradigm from action to stage, from reactive to proactive recruitment, from matching participants to the program

requirements to meeting the participant's demands in the program, and behavioral health programs that are focused on the clinics to the population whilst employing the field's most powerful personalized and collaborative intervention strategies (Prochaska, 1997). Methods for increasing self-efficacy used in this study includes mastery experience, verbal permission, enhancing physical and emotional states, and social modelling. The success of a person in attaining increasingly challenging routines of behaviors that are desirable is produced and made possible by their mastery experience. Verbal persuasion can boost confidence as much as necessary to provoke the initial endeavors toward a change of behavior may start by simply telling them they can do it. In addition, physical and emotional state improvement comprises endeavors to lessen stress and depression whilst developing positive emotions. The small steps carried in the realization of a complex objective is well explained and demonstrated in social modelling (Bandura 1997, Glanz et al., 2008). Another theorist in the name of Richard Lazarus also explains the concept of appraisal in his cognitive theory. Appraisal is the person's assessment of the meaning of what is happening for their well-being. Coping on the other hand is the person's attempts in thought and action to accomplish a specific demand. Both are said to play a role in changing oneself and/or adapting to the environment.

Emphasis on educational approach to health promotion is the essential starting point of another well-known framework in health promotion by Jackie Green (2010) PRECEDE-PROCEED (Predisposing Reinforcing and Enabling Constructs in Educational/Environmental Diagnosis and Evaluation-Policy Regulatory and Organizational Constructs in Educational and Environmental Development). This provides a structure for the application of theories and concepts methodically for developing and accessing changes in health behavior programs. However, this model

does not predict nor explain the relationship among factors thought to be associated with an outcome of interest. Nevertheless, the educational approach is concerned with enabling people to make informed choices, while the preventive approach sought application of psychological theory to achieve behavioral change. The assumption was that if people were given the “right” knowledge, they would act appropriately.

Theoretical Framework

The concept of this research study is to investigate the effect of a post-stroke program that provides supportive-educative teaching and intervention on the quality of life of older adults’ post-cerebral stroke survivors. This study is based upon the integration of the concept of Dorothea Orem’s Self-care Theory among other related health promotion disciplines and behavioral theories.

Dorothea Orem Self-Care Deficit Theory

Dorothea Elizabeth Orem believed that nursing ought to be perceived as a field of both knowledge and of practice. Self-care needs that are goal-oriented activities “are set towards producing interest in the part of the client to sustain life and health development”. Self-care increases and the person’s ability to attend to this need is when the nursing care comes in. Oftentimes, Orem represents health based on preventive healthcare. This model incorporates the advancement and preservation of health, including the treatment of disease or injury, as well as the prevention of complications.

Nursing is an art, a service, and a technology according to Dorothea Orem. Nurses uses intellect and creativity in planning to be able to support others in the design, provision, and management of systems of self-care. The five diverse methods

of assisting that nurses make use accordingly depending on situations are acting for or doing for another, guiding another, supporting another, providing an environment that promotes personal development in relation to becoming able to meet present or future demands for action and, teaching another. In helping individuals or groups to maintain self-care, nursing alongside health service is deliberately and purposively selected and performed actions, of which an interpersonal process transpires.

This study will operate on persons with functional abilities or those who have been taken to a peak level following a stroke (Stage 5) using the methods mentioned above. The Nursing agency at this stage is fully operative. Components of nursing agency includes theoretical knowledge on Stage 1-4, which includes the usual deficits and rehabilitative modalities of stroke-survivors, justification and anticipated effects of ongoing treatment regimen, family collaboration; health status monitoring skills using history taking and physical assessment, and to identify signs of functional decline or impending incident of stroke, performing home, family, or community assessment, making referrals, health counselling for individuals and small groups, and the capacity to develop relationships with the client that are based on trust and giving them support and acting as their advocate.

Health is a state of wholeness or integrity of the individual human being, his parts, and his methods of operating (Orem, 1980, cited by McKenna 2006). The immediate environment impacts the internal interaction of a character of a person. The role of nurses is to assist patients in determining or recognize possible means to execute self-care activities that are directed towards independence (Orem, cited by Octaviano et al., 2008). Nursing as a supportive-educative system provides a theoretical foundation for studies focusing on rehabilitation (Orem, 2003).

Figure 1. Orem's self-care client-centered theory

Within Orem's supportive-educative system, it is vital to note that the nurse's position as educator is just as crucial as to the rehabilitation nurse. According to Orem, human functioning is a combination of physical, psychological, interpersonal, and social, and through this integrated system, the person can advance and discover. This is in line with Florence Nightingale's concept of a person -a complex and holistic being- wherein the objective of nursing is to foster health within the patient and demonstrate an advocacy that gives power to the caring nurse through the utilization of intellect, personal motivation, and available opportunities, which comprises multidisciplinary collaboration and involvement of the community (Bostridge, 2008; Cook 1913; Dossey, 2000 cited in Selanders, 2012).

Orem's self-care being client centered theory, is focused on the needs and problems of clients. The importance of the client's endeavors to contribute to his or her own health is strongly associated with the emphasis of the person's accomplishment and preservation of independence in rehabilitation (Johnston, 1989, cited by Johnson et al., 2012). Orem's self-care client-centered theory as applied (Figure 1).

Post stroke clients may still have residual functional deficits. Older adult stroke

survivors may have comorbidities and other factors that need to be considered. This dictates a need to modify the approach, for instance in implementing exercises, and enlist participation from caregivers if possible. Furthermore, basic physiological needs (oxygen, water, food, water, temperature-clothing/shelter, sleep) safety and security needs (fall prevention) love and belongingness (family support) self-esteem need (increased self-efficacy) should have been met before self-actualization is to take place according to Maslow.

According to WHO (1986) as mentioned by Green (2010) there are three identified broad strategies to promote health based on the first International Conference on Health Promotion: One is advocacy to safeguard the establishment of conditions that promotes health. Another is through enabling individuals (Laverack et al., 2001; Green et al., 2010), by providing an environment that supports them in making healthy choices, through delivering the right information and skills important to them. Lastly, is through negotiation between various parties to ensure the interest of health. A health promotion initiative therefore begins with an advocacy on a particular health issue which aims to enable people by providing a helping environment through systematic planning, and community/organization involvement.

Conceptual Framework

The role of nurses in stroke prevention is deemed important in the clinical setting and not only for primary but in the secondary prevention. For that to take place, the patient needs to learn new knowledge, acquire skills, and develop positive attitudes to increase their self-care supply and meet their self-care demand after the stroke event.

Utilizing Dorothea Orem's client centered, grand theory of Self-care Deficit, this study operates in both science and art in assisting clients to improve their quality of

life, and how client's volition or self-determined behavior affect their life despite the presence of disease. The respondents are assessed and classified according to their level of function (Figure 1) where functionally independent individuals will be qualified to participate in the program. A supportive-educative nursing intervention is provided with the goal of strengthening the self-care supply of strokes survivors. Increasing the skills, knowledge, and attitude of stroke survivors is assumed to directly or indirectly increase their QOL.

The independent variable, supportive-educative program, is presumed to enhance the Quality of Life (dependent variable) of post-stroke older adults. Thus, it is the intention of this study to explore their QOL in four domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environmental.

Figure 2. Conceptual framework

Operational Definition

1. Quality of life – the perception of a person of their situation in life in based on their culture and value systems as well as in relation to their objectives, expectations, ideals, and concerns. The multi-dimensional nature of QOL is measured using WHOQOL-BREF tool covering its varied facets and domains. QOL is also subjective and is likewise reliant on the interpretation and insights of the person (Ziller 1974 cited in Mukherjee 2013)
2. Physical health – refers to the domain of QOL that measures facets like their daily movements, therapeutic substance necessity and medical assistances, strength and tiredness, movement, discomfort, sleep and rest, and ability to work. There are common activity limitations post-stroke such as hemiplegia, spasticity, and aphasia that limits the participant’s ability to perform. A tool recommended by the Stroke Association, Barthel’s index, measures activities indicating functional capacity that include feeding, bathing, grooming, dressing, elimination capacity, and mobility will be utilized in this study.
3. Psychological health – this includes aspects of physical impression and appearance, feelings, self-esteem, beliefs, faith, spirituality, reasoning, understanding, recollection, and focus.
4. Social relationships – assess the person’s affairs with others in the community, societal or group support, as well as their sensual activity with their respective partners.
5. Environment – this includes facets of financial resources, freedom, physical and security, health and social care, accessibility and quality, home environment, opportunities for acquiring new information and skills, participation in and

opportunities for recreation/leisure activities, physical environment, and transport.

6. Supportive-Educative Program – pertains to the protocol administered to the experimental group which addresses the domains of physical, psychological, social relationships, and environment. The program will utilize Dorothea Orem's theory on Nursing System focusing on supportive-educative nursing which focus on the nurse's role in meeting the patient's self-care demands with the patient cooperation in a supportive environment.
7. Older Stroke Survivors – older adult patients, aging 60 years and above who have been previously diagnosed with stroke and have recovered, have had a full rehabilitation program and are independent per Barthel's Index classification, with a history of stroke or the sudden neurologic insult that results from restriction or cessation of flow through the arterial supply system (Price and Wilson, 2003) which may be hemorrhagic or Ischemic.
8. Older adults defined as people who are 60 years and above that qualifies the inclusion criteria. They are further categorized as young-old (60-69), middle-old (70-80), old-old (80 and above).
9. Biophysical measures – refers to the cardiovascular measures which includes blood pressure (BP), mean arterial pressure (MAP), heart rate (HR), weight (Wt). These are going to be measured before (baseline) and a month after the supportive educative program commences. BP and HR will be monitored before and after every session, after 60 minutes. In addition, these biophysical measures will again be measured two months after the commencement of the supportive educative program.

10. Blood pressure – the tension of the blood in the circulatory system which determines the cardiac output and the peripheral vascular resistance. Ideally, the rhythmic ejection of blood into the aorta of an adult or simply called systolic blood pressure (SBP) is <120 mmHg. While the diastolic blood pressure (DBP) is < 80 mmHg, and depending on the quantity of related risk factors, the risk of stroke in hypertensive individuals occurs over an eightfold (Kannel, 1996). Hypertension in the elderly population (65-74 years of age) of the US ranges from 60% (Carol Porth, 2006).
11. Mean arterial pressure – refers to the average blood pressure in the systemic circulation, computed by adding one third of the pulse pressure to the diastolic blood pressure (DBP+PP/3) which is approximately 90 to 100 mmHg, denoting the average pressure in the arterial system during ventricular contraction and relaxation that indicates tissue perfusion.
12. Heart rate – refers to the speed of the heartbeat measured by counting the number of beats in one minute (bpm). This will be measured before the start of the session and 5-10 minutes post exercise.
13. Age – measures the stroke survivor's chronological age. Recorded by the number of years a person has lived.
14. Sex – dichotomized as male or female.
15. Civil Status – categorized as single, married, separated, widowed.
16. Educational Status – categorized by their educational level is classified as postgraduate, college graduate, college level, vocational course, high school graduate, high school level, elementary graduate, elementary level, or no formal education.

Research Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant difference between the biophysical profile of older adult stroke survivors before and after the SEP.

H2: There is a significant difference between the QOL of older adult post-stroke survivors before and after the supportive-educative program.

H3: There is a significant relationship between QOL and their (a) Age (b) Sex (c) Civil Status (d) Educational Status

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methodology of the investigation. The methodology includes the research design, study population, sampling technique, instrumentation/tool, sampling design, sampling setting, research design, data gathering procedure, bioethical considerations, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study utilized the mixed methods explanatory sequential design. This method uses quantitative data to describe, compare, and relate variables integrated with qualitative data derived from focus group discussion. This is followed by the collection of the qualitative data as illustrated in Figure 2.1. Mixed method design combines qualitative and quantitative approaches within different phases of the research process (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998) that permits a more complete and synergistic utilization of data (Wisdom & Creswell, 2013).

The preliminary quantitative phase utilized a questionnaire with Likert scaled items for pre-test and post-test (close-ended). Homogeneity was maintained by focusing on the older adult population with the same developmental level and post-stroke status who have finished formal rehabilitation and are willing to participate in the study. Implementing a pre-qualifying test to participants in addition to the qualifying criteria is deemed necessary for the respondent's safety as well as cost-effective and time saving which fits the allotted budget and timeframe of the investigator. The investigation also measured biophysical changes as supported by a change in blood pressure, MAP, heart rate, weight prior to and subsequently the SEP.

The qualitative data collection for this study employed semi structured, in-depth individual interview and group discussion using guided questions (open-ended), which permits the interviewer to probe into societal and intimate affairs and wide range of experiences of the respondents (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree 2006) explore the narratives, encounters, points of view, ideas, desires and concerns of individual. (Kitzinger 2005 as cited by Liamputtong 2011)

The variables explored SEP as the independent variable and the perception of QOL as the dependent variable, indicating changes in four domains, namely: psychological, social relationships, environmental, and physical health.

Figure 3. Mixed methods explanatory sequential design phases

Study Population

The target population for this study were older adults aging 60 years old and in Metro Manila, who were stable and able to participate and understand simple instructions, functionally independent based on Barthel’s Index. However, exclusions of the following were considered necessary in favor of safety of the participants (and other participants) and resources available in conducting the investigation: 1.) Physically dependent and with sensory disabilities such as blindness, deafness, mobility problem 2.) Neurological and psychiatric illness which affects mood, cognition,

and movement 3.) Older persons that were home-bound.

Sampling Technique

Non-probability purposive sampling was used in this investigation. This technique is widely applied to recognize and develop the range of disparity, parallel to the utilization of quantifiable measures to describe the unpredictability or distribution of values for a particular variable quantity (Palinkas et al., 2016) for identification of data rich cases for most effective use of limited resources (Patton, 2002) selecting knowledgeable as well as experienced persons with the phenomenon of interest (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011) that are obtainable and willing to take part and able to share their experience (Bernard 2002; Spradley 1979). Using specific eligibility criteria, respondents were hand-picked. Participants were previously diagnosed stroke or have survived stroke that are currently living in the community, have graduated from formal physical rehabilitation, able to ambulate, able to give informed consent, and able to follow simple instructions. Samples were taken from the age of 60 and above and were classified as Young Old (60 to 69 years), Middle Old (70 to 79 years), and Old Old (80 years and up).

Through network sampling or snowball sampling, the investigator gathered qualified respondents from the two barangays, stroke support organization, Senior Citizen's group, disability group and per referrals. This method is frequently applied when the target population is with characteristics who might otherwise be challenging to recognize (Polit et al., 2003). Due to the study's specification and relatively high possibility of attrition in interventional study specifically in older adults, it was deemed necessary to enlist as many participants as possible.

The time of diagnosis required was more than 6 months or greater to assure

that respondents are well adjusted to their post-stroke conditions and have a more stable state. Comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular was excluded and was considered part of the condition of the respondents for as long as they are compliant with their medications.

Research Setting

The investigation was initially conducted in two locations: the Clinic for Therapy Service in University of the Philippines Manila, and in the barangay halls of the selected barangay for orientation and was continued in Diabetes Care Center in Manila Medical Hospital or ManilaMed (previously known as Medical Center Manila), through the entirety of the program. The respondents were gathered in the barangay halls of Barangay 670 and Barangay 695, zone 75. The senior citizen's group Office of the Senior Citizen Affairs Head (OSCA) in Manila City Hall was tapped in the investigation under the qualifying criteria set for the study. Barangay hall of 670 is in Bacobo Street, Ermita and is composed of 39 registered senior citizens, while barangay 695, zone 75 which is located along Singalong Street, Malate is composed of 47 registered senior citizens at the time of the study.

ManilaMed's Diabetes Care Center was the venue for study group respondents who were from the other districts of Manila. Participants from stroke organizations such as the Department of Rehabilitation Medicine Stroke Support Group and those referred by ManilaMed's rehabilitation center were accommodated in the center as well. The Diabetes Care Center mainly provides diabetes education, lifestyle and nutritional management services for diabetic patients, a segment of the Wellness department of the hospital which is located at the 6th floor of the building. ManilaMed is a tertiary hospital with 250 bed-capacity is in UN Avenue corner General Luna, Metro Manila.

Figure 4. Research protocol

Data Collection Methods and Procedures

Step 1: Preparation of the Intervention Protocol

Employing Dorothea Orem's Self-care Deficit theory, the investigator utilized self-care nursing systems and its components, results of previous research studies related to Orem's theory and stroke survivor's QOL, and developed interventions that are congruent to the needs of the four components of QOL: physical health, psychological, social relationships and environmental.

Step 2: Permission to Proceed

The investigator discussed the investigation with the research panel and secured permission from the Ethical and Review Board.

Step 3: Coordination with Point Persons

The investigator coordinated with the Barangay Chairmans of selected barangays, Senior Citizen's groups (Office of the Senior Citizens Association), stroke organization (DRM stroke support group), Rehabilitation Center Clinic (ManilaMed) to gather as many participants as possible. Discussion on how the data collection process took place and was undertaken with initial orientation of participants conducted in the barangay office or clinic.

Step 4: Training of a Research Assistant

To prevent research bias, research assistants will be deployed in the investigation. Prior to the commencement of the investigation, they will be oriented to the investigation's objectives and methodology. A registered nurse currently working in the chosen area of study is preferred, with or without prior experience in research.

After the selection, they attended a four-hour orientation-workshop wherein familiarization of the investigation's concepts, definitions, and methodology, and procedures was instituted. The roles and responsibilities of the research assistant

before, during, and after the investigation was discussed. They were oriented with the selection criteria of the samples, the theories and concepts applied in the investigation and the tools to be used in the collection of data. Their knowledge and skills of the investigation was assessed through summary recall and return demonstration.

The research assistants were able to screen the eligibility of the respondents, explain the purpose of the investigation and secure informed consent prior to the intervention. The conduction of pre-test and post-test was administered before and after the intervention by the research assistant as part of his/her task.

Step 5: Preserving the Sensitivity of the Instrument

In order to ensure cross-cultural adaptation, the investigator had to do the following:

Translation: Two professional translators from the University of the Philippines translated the instruments used in the investigation from English to Tagalog.

Back-translation: The translated Tagalog versions was then translated back to the source language for the purpose of validating the quality of the instrument. The two back-translators who are experts in Tagalog should have no knowledge about the objectives of the investigation.

Committee review: The translated instrument was reviewed by expert investigators to generate comments and suggestions to improve the reliability of the translated instrument.

Pre-testing of the instrument: A sample population of ten participants was invited to carry out the approved translated instrument to determine the reliability of the instrument.

Step 6: Comparison group- Data Collection

Once eligible based on the investigation's criteria, informed consent was

secured, providing the complete information of the investigation's objectives, risks and benefits and the rights as participants. Once the consent was secured, the research assistant will ask the participants to fill up a pre-coded demographic sheet, Barthel's Index, and QOL questionnaire. A Health Promotion Program was conducted thrice a week for one hour in a span of one month, for a total of 12 sessions.

Step 7: Data Handling

The research assistant was responsible for ensuring the completeness and accuracy of every form pertinent to the data collection. Repeated measures were done and the data was entered in a secure file until the sample size has been reached and fit to be analyzed. The files were sealed in an envelope and stored in a locked cabinet for safekeeping, while electronic data will be password-protected. Reproduction of data for commercial and profit use was not allowed. Research assistants were not allowed to bring home the forms and may only have access to it during the intervention.

Data Gathering Methods and Procedure

Prior to the commencement of the investigation, the approval of the University of the Philippines Ethics Review Board was obtained. Permission from the Barangay Chairman in Brgy. 695 zone 75, Brgy. 670, and ManilaMed was secured. To enlist participants in the investigation, permission was asked from the point persons of the Senior Citizens groups in District V. The WHOQOL Group was asked to allow the investigator to use the questionnaire and grant access to the instrument in Tagalog version.

WHOQOL-BREF tool was pre-tested to determine its validity and reliability. As deemed necessary, revisions were made after consulting experts and the owners of the tool. This was followed by recruitment of research assistants who will conduct the

SEP to the respondents. Qualified research assistants were trained to provide the SEP in a uniform manner and were assigned to the investigation and comparison group using double blind to contend with a double Hawthorne effect. Being qualified as a participant of a study appears to affect the way people behave, thereby concealing the effect of the variable of interest (Polit et al., 2003).

The identified participants were oriented to the intervention protocol and once amenable, consent was obtained. Then the participants were asked to answer Barthel's Index and the Filipino Short Portable Mental Status Questionnaire. The former will provide the data that signified the functional independence of the participant, and the latter helped identify the presence of depression. Depression is an extremely common condition after stroke (National Stroke Association, 2010) thus a psychological assessment tool is deemed necessary as part of the qualifying criteria. Informed consent was secured once they qualified. The participant's anonymity and confidentiality were maintained using codes in record keeping. All records were only viewed by the investigator and were not shared to other individuals for any other purpose. The Ethics Review Committee, auditors and other regulatory authorities viewed the records for verification only. Research assistants were not permitted to reproduce or bring home the forms and only have access to it during the intervention. The records were sealed in an envelope and stored in a locked cabinet for safekeeping, while electronic data was password-protected.

Prior to the commencement of SEP and after the program, the respondents were asked to fill up a 24-hour diet and activity recall with the goal to acquire a baseline pre-SEP data of their diet and activity and at the same time, encourage awareness in what they were eating and/or drinking. After the SEP, they are also made to complete the same questionnaire to compare the data after approximately a month from the

beginning of their sessions.

The participants and facilitators also interviewed post-SEP to further delve into the quality of life of older adult stroke survivors. Semi-structured in-depth interviews were utilized using the internet and social networking platform as the medium of gathering data, to gain more insights using open-ended questions about their personal experience with stroke, as well as feedback on their participation in the study. The process of mixed methods explanatory sequential process is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 5. Mixed methods explanatory sequential steps

Research Instrumentation

The questionnaire WHOQOL-BREF created by WHOQOL Group was adapted to determine the quality of life of older adult post stroke survivors. WHOQOL-BREF is a condensed version of the WHO QOL 100 questions and was used for both pre-test and post-test. Pre-test was given prior to the commencement of intervention and after a month. Post-test was given after one month of intervention.

The instrument comprises 26 items that incorporate various domains classified as physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment which influences the total QOL and wellbeing of a person in general. WHOQOL-BREF is applicable cross-culturally, a reliable tool with a good internal consistency, test-retest reliability, as well as discriminate, criterion, and concurrent validity (Rashid, 2013). 24 facets were incorporated in the tool's four domains (physical, psychological, social relationship, environment). Permission from WHOQOL Group was secured before the use of the tool. This tool was used and tested already on 12 populations including Acute Stroke (n=202, mean age=72) Chronic Stroke (n=74; mean age=58.35), Traumatic Brain Injury (n=199) Community Dwelling Older Adults (n=1200, mean age=73.4). Conducted in 15 culturally diverse fields, four of which are in Asia (Bangkok, New Delhi, Madras, Tokyo) and translated in 19 different languages worldwide. Its internal consistency for the four domains is excellent, except Social Relationships which is only adequate (Chronbach's alpha= 0.73) by Hwang, 2003, and Excellent in all domains by Lucas-Carrasco, 2011 (Chronbach's alpha=0.88) and was repeatedly tested over several studies for its reliability and validity.

Quantitative data of the study also includes the biophysical measurements. This was recorded in a data collection sheet containing the participant's blood pressure, heart rate, MAP, and weight and was monitored every meeting, and the weight on a

weekly basis. The blood pressure machine, stethoscope, and weighing scale used in the study were evaluated for quality prior to the commencement of the study to ensure accuracy and functionality.

Semi-structured in-depth interviews with open-ended questions were utilized in this study for qualitative data collection. The participants were free to respond as they wish, while researchers probed their responses. This provides a broad interpretation of the concerns by means of their written explanation (Jamshed 2014) allowing participants to personally convey themselves or experiences at their own pace (Corbin & Morse, 2003). This ascertains the study population's insights about an experience relating to the subject of the study, which play an important role in mixed-method research (McIntosh et al., 2015).

Data Analysis

All data was encoded, and statistical tests were run using IBM SPSS Statistics under 0.05 significance level. Nominal data such as sex was presented in percentage distribution. Ordinal data/interval data such as age, body weight, blood pressure, heart rate, MAP was presented using measures of central tendency particularly means and standard deviations. Statistical methods to be utilized in this investigation shall be as follows:

- 1) Descriptive Statistics: This was utilized to ascertain the occurrence and percentage of the profile of the participants and all the investigation variables.
- 2) Paired t-test: This was applied to determine the difference of QOL on item level between pre-test and post-test of the respondents.
- 3) Independent t-test: This was used to determine the difference of QOL on item level on post-test of the respondents.

4) Wilcoxon signed rank test- This was used as an alternative to the paired student's t-test due to the small sample size and the distribution of the two samples' means cannot be assumed to be normally distributed.

Qualitative Data

Thematic analysis was applied in the study to interpret the gathered data. This was done by reading the transcripts multiple times until preliminary codes were assigned in each content.

The researcher and two research assistants individually undertook the analytic approach initially and then together, finalized the data by grouping it to codes and themes, focusing on the substance or contextual value of the text (Budd et al., 1967; Lindkvist, 1981; McTavish & Pirro, 1990; Tesch, 1990) in verbal, print, or electronic form obtained from open-ended survey questions, one-on-one interview, and focus groups discussion (Kondracki & Wellman, 2002). The process includes the identification and quantification of the words or content at first and then grouping them into themes. Calculating in numerical value to recognize patterns in the data and to contextualize the codes (Morgan, 1993) with special attention on identifying the different facets of quality of life.

Summative content analysis scheme was utilized utilizing codes derived from the transcripts. This approach employs text as individual phrases or relative to a certain subject, rather than evaluating the data (Hsieh et al., 2005) is especially valuable for complicated texts and works best with diverse data which has the possibility to produce a variety of perceptions and thoughts (Rapport, 2010). Identification of forms paved the way to clarification of related significance or contextual meaning of specific phrases or subject (Hsieh et al, 2005, Morgan 1993) discover inherent implications of

the phrases (Babbie, 1992; Catanzaro, 1988; Morse & Field, 1995). This helps demonstrate that the verbatim evidence is in line with the analysis of the study (Webber 1990).

The qualitative phase seeks to contextualize the respondent's feelings and emotions by collecting, analyzing, and integrating it to the quantitative data. Incorporation of the qualitative data to the quantitative data is the final step of the process where inferences are derived from both data. The purpose of mixed methods is to deliver a better insight of a research problem or the topic of the study than either research methodology only (Creswell, 2007). This is utilized when there is adequate empirical information about an experience or phenomenon, but the subjective understanding is deficient (Merton & Kendall, 1946; Morse & Field, 1995; Richards & Morse, 2007).

Ethical Considerations

The investigator safeguards the rights of the people participating in the research. Confidentiality was ensured at all levels which was clearly specified in the consent form. If the participant decided to withdraw from the investigation, he/she was free to do so, and the confidentiality of data contributed to investigation such as demographics and responses to the tools was maintained and secured. The rights and dignity of the participants was protected. To secure the consent, all pertinent details were discussed to the understanding of the respondents. Cultural sensitivity and respect were maintained all throughout the investigation.

All qualified participants were given equal chances to be included in this investigation, discrimination and biases in the selection process was avoided. The investigation applied necessary measures so as not to cause harm to the participants.

This included the limitation of time and data to be gathered in the investigation, and the measurement of physiological parameters before and after the activity. The investigation aims to enhance wellness and promote lifestyle change to the target population. Equal rights, benefits were provided to the respondents of the investigation. Previous scholarly works related to this investigation were ensured proper citation in this manuscript.

The research did not include administration of any drug or medication to the participants and this was fully disclosed during the briefing of the purpose of the investigation and the signing of the consent. Transportation allowance was provided as well as snacks during sessions, however, no monetary gifts was given.

Anonymity was maintained through use of code numbers to track records. The data sheets can only be viewed by the investigator and are not to be used for profit-oriented purposes. As mentioned, research assistants had access to the forms but only limited to the time of intervention hence, they were not allowed to bring the forms home or reproduce for any purposes. Ethics Review Committee and regulatory authorities may have access to the records for verification purposes only. The records were kept in a sealed envelope and stored in a locked cabinet for safekeeping. The electronic data and softcopy of reports was password-protected.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter will discuss the findings of the data collated and its analysis. Due to the limitations of the study such as the sample deficiency and weakness in data collection strategy, Wilcoxon signed rank test, was utilized for the statistical interpretation of the study to ensure the provision of a better presentation of the result and analysis of the data and has been adapted in consideration of the limits.

In total, there were 17 older adult individuals who qualified and filled out the WHO QOL-BREF questionnaires. There were 2 attritions during data collection, thus two questionnaires that were filled up were excluded from the study as the respondents were unable to complete the whole program for medical and personal reasons. All 15 respondents were controlled for baseline characteristics such as gender, sex, education level. Among all 17 older adult participants, 88.23 % completed SEP with 97.22 % attendance to prescheduled classes.

The presence of multi-morbidity and associated high rate of mortality in older adults with stroke make this population a challenging group to obtain and recruit. Although roughly three-quarters of stroke cases happen in persons aged ≥ 65 years (Yousufuddin et al., 2019) and is the top three leading cause of disability among in this age group (Teh et al., 2018) epidemiologic data have been relatively sparse in Asian populations (Thammaroj et al., 2005) such as Philippines, and post-stroke death is greater among people of underprivileged communities (Osypuk et al., 2018; Brown et al., 2013) such as where the researcher conducted the study.

Thus, the accessible population may not be representative of the target population in this study and the information derived is only from the available data that

was extracted which will be further discussed in this chapter.

Table 1

Demographic Profile of the Study Population (n=15)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage %
Sex		
Male	9	60
Female	6	40
Age (year)		
Young-old (60-69)	7	46.66
Middle-old (70-80)	6	40
Old-old (80-and above)	2	13.33
Education		
Elementary	2	13.33
High School	3	20
College	8	53.33
Vocational	2	13.33
Marital Status		
Single	2	13.33
Married	8	53.33
In a Relationship (not married)	1	6.66
Separated	1	6.66
Widowed	3	20
Employment type		
Working	3	20
Non-working	12	80
Expenses		
Pension	6	40
Spouse	2	13.33
Children	2	13.33
Pension & Children	1	6.66
Pension & Spouse	1	6.66
Pension & Savings	1	6.66
Pension & Business	1	6.66
Spouse & Children	1	6.66
Senior Citizen Member		
Yes	3	20
No	12	80

Demographic Profile

Age

Looking at Table 1, it could be considered that the mean age of the study population was from the middle-old, aged group (70-80). Of all participants who completed, the majority of them were male: 6 were female (40 %), with a mean age of 69 years old and 9 people (60 %) were male with a mean age of 71 years old.

The age is a factor in stroke that affects a specific age group in the population and at the same time plays a role in rehabilitation outcomes. This is consistent with a cross-sectional epidemiological survey in Singapore Elderly study that says older age and male gender are associated with greater stroke risk (Sacco et al., 1997). Almost 75% of strokes occurrence are observed in people 65 and older and the risk double over each decade after the age of 55 (Stroke Statistics by The Internet Stroke Center, U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 2019.) Age is also a factor in QOL, in a study of stroke patients (n=327) the youngest group (<44 years old) revealed the biggest progress in functional outcome and QOL score in the areas of physical and social domains compared to >65 years old (Manimmanakorn et al., 2008). Very old (≥80 years) stroke patients are at risk of deterioration in handicap with time (Kwok et al., 2007) as well as associated low QOL (Chuluunbaatar et al., 2016). However, in this study, it is difficult and impossible to decipher improvements and compare results based on sub-ages due to deficiency of the number of respondents.

Sex

The respondents (n=15) consisted of 60% female and 40% male, with an average age of 70.93 years old. The youngest among the respondents was 64 and the eldest was 82 years old. A big margin of the respondents belonged to the young-

old age group which consisted of 46.66% of the respondents and the least from the old-old age group (80 years old and above) with 13.33%.

In the Philippines, the predominance of stroke was twofold higher among men in comparison to women in 40 years older as well as younger population groups based on a 1999 community-based survey (Navarro et al., 2014) and is deemed the top 2 main cause of death overall. As claimed by a Singapore Elderly study, male gender (and older age) is closely linked with a greater chance of having a stroke (Sacco et al., 1997). In America, stroke happens to one out of 5 women in her lifetime and is the 5th major reason of death in men (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2019). A multivariate analyses study corroborated that being a woman was a compelling aspect of critical stroke with the mean age more dominant in female than in male respondents (80 ± 8 versus 75 ± 9 years, $P < .00001$).

Marital Status

Majority of the respondents are married (53.33%). 13.33% are single, 6.66% are in a relationship, while the rest are either separated 6.66% or widowed 20%. In some studies, being married is considered predictive factors associated with significant decrease in physical and environmental QOL in one of the studies among handicapped stroke survivors in Hong Kong (Kwok et al., 2007) while being single was associated with low QOL (Chuluunbaatar et al., 2016).

Education, Employment and Expenses

In general, the respondents were college graduates (53%) and are non-working (80%). It is noteworthy that most of them depend solely on their pension (40%) while some depend on their spouse or children (13%) and a few of them have a combination

of the above mentioned or from a business source (6%).

It is remarkable that a good sum of the respondents is not officially a member of the Senior Citizen group. Despite the benefits and privileges entitled to a registered Senior Citizens member such as access to social services, financial assistance (Republic Act 9257, Senior Citizens Act of 2003) only 3 out of 15 are officially a member. Some of the respondents claim they have lost their identification cards and never got a new one, while some claim they are more active in the Stroke group than the Senior Citizen's because of the sense of "belongingness" and camaraderie within the group, wherein they regularly meet weekly.

Lack of exercise is one of the associated factors with poor QOL and handicap along with old-age home residence and prescription of soft diets or tube feeding based on a study (n=303) (Kwok et al., 2007).

Biophysical Profile

The biophysical profile of older adult post cerebral stroke survivors before and after the SEP are discussed in terms of BP, MAP, Heart rate, and weight.

In general, the data implies that out of 15 respondents there were positive improvements in the systolic BP in 7 out of 15 cases (46.66%), diastolic BP in 5 out of 15 cases (33.33%), MAP in 6 out of 15 cases (40%), and weight in 8 out of 15 cases (53.33%) with an average weight of ± 0.206 kilograms.

Systolic Blood Pressure

The result in the graph shown in Figure 1, illustrates the systolic pressure of the cases prior to the commencement (blue line) of SEP and post 12 sessions (red line). Around 53.33% of the cases shows a decrease of systolic BP post SEP. Among 15

cases, there is one case with uncontrolled SBP for unidentified reasons and the rest are below 140 mmHg which can be considered controlled.

Figure 6. Systolic pressure of respondents before & after SEP

Remarkably, among all the respondents, case 12 presents the highest drop of systolic from 134 mmHg to 100 mmHg, while case 9 remained the same before and after the SEP. Oddly for most other cases, there was a reverse effect which shows a low systolic prior to SEP to a high systolic post-SEP intervention. Several factors influence systolic pressure such as stress, older age, salt intake, level of physical activity, smoking among others (Taylor et al., 2011). Interestingly, the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (Chobanian et al., 2004 JNC 7th Report) considers SBP elevations to be most crucial than DBP elevations in individuals 50 and above. In an investigation of impact of diastolic and systolic blood pressure on death concluded that mortality rate significantly increases at a SBP of ≥ 140 independent of DBP (Taylor et al., 2011).

In another study of stroke survivor, exhibited a J- or U-shaped curve implications between BP and the probability of subsequent of CVD events and mortality, with the minimum incident rates in the BP range of 110-119 systolic and 80-89 diastolic, while respondents with a BP lower than 110/70mmHg or 140/90 mmHg or greater had a remarkably raised threat of worse outcomes (Zhao et al., 2016). An interesting study conducted for a year (Feb 2010-Jan 2011) applying cross-sectional, retrospective, observational study in a multicenter with stroke patients ages 45 years above, concludes that the lack of patients' awareness along with insufficient antihypertensive use were the 2 extremely prevalent explanation of the patients' uncontrolled BP according to doctors (Nidhinandana et al., 2014).

Figure 7. Diastolic pressure of respondents before & after SEP

As can be seen, there were different trends of diastolic blood pressure (DBP) in all cases. In 3 out of 15 cases (33%), it shows a decrease in DBP with an average of 14.4 mmHg. The highest decrease of DBP is case number 5 (20mmHg) while the rest

either remained the same or greater than before. What is striking in the result is that there are 4 out of 15 cases that have inversely increased (37.5%) after the sessions with an average of 12.5 mmHg. These findings however are inconclusive owing to circumstances that are not included in this report.

Generally, the cases have either in control DBP or >90 mmHg. According to a study examining death based on the independent effects of diastolic and systolic blood pressure (Taylor et al., 2011), DBP is largely irrelevant in ages 50 years old and above and further describes that mortality rate of these individuals starts to rise with increasing DBP levels of over 90 in a progressive manner, claiming that DBP is a more important predictor of mortality for 50 years and below.

Heart Rate

The graph in Figure 8 shows the heart rate of respondents before and after SEP. Most of the cases had an increase of ± 4.46 bpm or 10.05% post SEP. While it is noteworthy that there is a stark drop of heart rate in cases 3, 7, and 9 with other cases showing a slight increase or have remained relatively the same prior to SEP implementation, it is still within the acceptable range and is negligible.

Figure 8. Heart rate of respondents before & after SEP

One worth mentioning is case 12, which appears to be below the normal range. It may be possible that this is somewhat expected and is unique to the participant, or that it may have been due to external factors. According to a study, a significant bradycardia which is ≤ 45 bpm or tachycardia which is ≥ 120 bpm are said to be a frequent phenomenon in acute stroke (Ritter et al., 2011). A heart rate may characterize a healing goal to enhance the status post ischemic stroke (Erdur et al., 2014), and in major-risk, high blood pressure patients with history of stroke/ TIA, resting heart rate was the most compelling determinant of persistent stroke (Sandset et al, 2014). In another study involving middle-aged and elderly Chinese population, elevated resting cardiac rate was intensely and distinctly associated with carotid atherosclerosis (Wang et al., 2016) an indication of cardiac complications which are common post-acute stroke and vice versa, cardiac disease is a recurrent cause of stroke (Ritter et al., 2011).

According to a study (n=1335) associating HR measured on admission and early

death in the hospital in patients with acute ischemic stroke, higher heart rate (HR \geq 83) is linked with unsatisfactory consequence (Erdur et al., 2014). In another multivariable analysis, a significant relationship between increased probability of stroke recurrence to the resting heart rate and diabetes mellitus at baseline (Sandset et al., 2014).

Weight in Kilograms

Figure 9. Weight of respondents before & after SEP

Weight

In general, there is no substantial change in the weight of the participants in all cases after SEP as shown in Figure 9. Overweight has been a known risk factor for ischemic stroke (Rohrmann 2019; Hajifathalian et al., 2014; Strazzullo et al., 2010). However, a Framingham observational study showed that fatality caused by cardiovascular was heightened for respondents who dropped weight compared to those who retained their weight (Higgins et al., 1993) and on middle aged participants who lost weight (Williamson et al., 1995; Yaari et al., 1998).

In an investigation of n=782 of how body weights affect survival after stroke in patients 71± years old shows that there may be indication of protective factors that are not known that is linked with modestly elevated body weight before stroke, demonstrating that overweight and mildly obese participants had better 10-year survival (after ischemic stroke) compared with normal-weight participants (Aparicio et al., 2017).

On the other hand, losing weight (greater than 3 kg) exclusively was associated with higher possibility of death(HR, 5.87; P = .001) while an increase in body weight of more than 5% of the baseline tended to be correlated with enhanced survivability in comparison to those without weight gain (log-rank test, P = .07) (Wohlfahrt et al., 2016), and the danger of ischemic stroke is progressively compounded (in those who lost or gained more than 5% of the weight)over four years (Rohrmann, 2019).

Figure 10. Mean arterial pressure of respondents before & after SEP

MAP

Mean arterial pressure (MAP) which is a time-weighted average over the whole cardiac cycle, provides a measure of the average perfusion pressure of the systemic circulation. Figure 10 shows the result of mean arterial pressure of respondents before and after SEP, 53.33% of respondent's MAP shows a decrease after the SEP program with an average of 9.74. On the other hand, there were 46.66% of the cases that appear to have a reverse effect post SEP with an average of 9.38. Prior to SEP, the majority of the respondents have normal MAP (70-100 mmHg) with two high cases (3%) which are >100mmHg.

The increase and/or decrease of MAP in the study are however inconclusive and needs to be conducted to a larger population to be generalizable. MAP, a well-recognized cardiovascular marker in various clinical settings, is calculated by multiplying diastolic blood pressure to two and adding the sum to systolic blood pressure [MAP = SBP + 2 (DBP)]. In general, a MAP of at least 60mmHg or greater is necessary to ensure perfusion to vital organs. Physicians usually consider anything between 70 to 100mmHg to be normal. A high MAP is considered 100mmHg and above indicating a lot of pressure in the arteries. MAP numerical values offer the closest approximation of central aortic pressure and is the main hemodynamic parameter monitored by neurohormonal system to control blood pressure. However, MAP values are not necessarily related to adequate peripheral perfusion and organ system function (McGhee et al., 2002) unless integrated with clinical assessment of patient's status.

In related studies conducted to post-stroke survivors, on a large-sectional study (n=6104) there is a close correlation with ischemic stroke with increased MAP level (Liqiang Zheng et al., 2008; Benetos et al., 1997; Millar, 1999; Mazza et al., 2001).

Moreover, MAP was said to be a better predictor of ischemic stroke (than pulse pressure) in diagnostic accuracy (Liqiang Zheng et al., 2008) while PP for coronary events (Millar et al., 1999).

In some analyses, MAP classification can be more advantageous specially in cases where a person might have normal systolic pressure but higher diastolic pressure or vice versa. In such cases, MAP compartmentalization could be beneficial for better inferential statistics and meaningful interpretation especially in studies addressing blood pressure and its associated covariates like cardiovascular diseases and type 2 diabetes for better understanding and preventive purposes (Kundu et al., 2017).

Quality of Life Domains

The QOL of respondents that were evaluated in the domains of Physical, Psychological, Social, and Environmental are presented in the following tables. Overall, Psychological domain score reflecting on negative feelings in appearance and self-esteem was observed low and Physical and Social domains was observed high indicating positive coping in their everyday activities and intimate relationships among others. In the following tables, the mean and standard deviation of each domain will be further discussed.

Illustrated in Table 2 are the mean and standard deviation of the physical domain quality of life Pre- and Post-SEP of respondents. The data shows that the respondents have a fair perception of their quality of life before (mean=3.504) and after SEP (mean=3.152) with a standard deviation of $sd < 1$ prior to SEP implying that the respondent's scores vary from one another in a high extent and is expected. It can be noted that standard deviation is more variable ($sd > 1.2794$) post-SEP which could

mean that the participant's perception of their physical quality of life grow more variable.

Table 2

Means Scores of the Physical Domain Among Respondents

Question Q3 + Q4 + Q10 + Q15 + Q16 + Q17 + Q18	Mean	STDEV Pre/ Post
To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?	2.800	1.0823
	3.000	1.0690
How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?	2.733	1.0823
	3.000	1.069
Do you have enough energy for everyday life?	3.400	0.8281
	3.200	0.5606
How well are you able to get around?	3.200	0.7746
	3.266	0.5936
How satisfied are you with your sleep?	3.333	0.8997
	3.400	0.9103
How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities?	3.133	0.9904
	3.133	0.6399
How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?	2.933	1.0997
	3.066	0.7037
	3.504	0.9713
Overall	3.152	1.2794

Table 3 presents the mean scores of the respondents in the QOL physical domain. Data shows that the respondents have decreased assessment scores from a moderate level of psychological quality of life perception pre-SEP (Mean=3.244) to slightly below average post-SEP (mean=2.966) with a standard deviation of 0.7921 and 0.8950 respectively. This implies that the respondent's perception of their psychological QOL is neither high nor low and the standard deviation suggests that most believe that their psychological QOL is within the middle range. Among the 4 domains, psychological QOL scored the lowest. Interestingly, when asked about to

what extent they feel their life is meaningful, the respondents answered the highest (Mean=3.8) which denotes that they view their life to be a lot meaningful.

Table 3

Means Scores of the Psychological Domain Among Respondents

Question	Q5 + Q6 + Q7 + Q11 + Q19 + Q26	Mean	STDEV Pre/Post
How much do you enjoy life?		3.000	0.7559
To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?		2.866	0.9155
		4.000	0.9258
		3.600	0.9103
How well are you able to concentrate?		3.333	0.8165
		3.266	0.8837
Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?		3.533	1.3020
		2.533	0.9155
How satisfied are you with yourself?		3.266	1.0998
		3.200	1.0142
How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression?		2.333	0.7237
		2.333	0.6172
	Overall	3.244	0.7921
		2.966	0.8950

Table 4 presents the mean scores of the social domain among respondents. The standard deviation (mean=3.399) is almost identical standard deviation before and after the program (mean=3.444) which is consistent with figure 4.6 and figure 4.7, indicating a constant social QOL among respondents. This could mean that respondents have good personal relationships and social support and perceive their social quality of life to be fair. Interestingly, it is observed that the respondents have the highest satisfaction (mean=4.133) in their personal relationships under the social domain which also appears to be the highest mean score among other questions in all domains.

Table 4

Means Scores of the Social Domain Among Respondents

Question	Q20 + Q21 + Q22	Mean	STDEV Pre/ Post
How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?		4.133	1.0601
		4.133	1.1255
How satisfied are you with your sex life?		3.000	1.1339
		3.000	1.2536
How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?		3.066	0.8837
		3.200	1.0823
		3.399	0.6359
Overall		3.444	0.6048

Table 5 illustrates the mean scores of the environmental domain QOL among respondents. Data shows that the respondents perceived a medium level of environmental quality of life (mean=3.256) pre-SEP. This dropped to (mean=3.049) post-SEP implying issues mainly on financial resources (mean2.933/2.600), which is consistent with the major theme: poor financial capacity derived from the interview.

The results suggest that they are not satisfied with the available health care services and their financial resources but still overall perceive their environmental QOL to be fair (mean=3.049) post-SEP, suggesting it is not very high nor very low.

Table 5

Means Scores of the Environmental Domain Among Respondents

Question	Q8 + Q9 + Q12 + Q13 + Q14 + Q23 + Q24 + Q25	Mean	STDEV Pre/ Post
How safe do you feel in your daily life?		3.533	0.6399
		3.466	0.5164
How healthy is your physical environment?		3.533	0.6399
		3.266	0.5936

Question	Q8 + Q9 + Q12 + Q13 + Q14 + Q23 + Q24 + Q25	Mean	STDEV Pre/ Post
Have you enough money to meet your needs?		2.933	0.7988
		2.600	0.7368
How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?		3.266	1.1629
		3.133	0.8338
To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?		3.200	0.7746
		3.133	0.8338
How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?		3.333	1.1127
		3.266	0.9612
How satisfied are you with your access to health services?		3.133	0.6399
		2.800	1.0142
How satisfied are you with your transport?		3.133	0.9155
		2.733	0.8837
Overall		3.256	0.4062
		3.049	0.3039

Figure 11. PRE- SEP QOL of respondents in 4 domains

Figure 11 is the scatterplot diagram presentation of the Pre-SEP QOL of respondents in the four domains: Physical in blue diamond, Psychological in red square, Social in green triangle, and Environmental in purple X.

Largely, it can be observed that the environmental domain has the highest QOL score among the 4 areas evaluated. Among the four domains, Social is the lowest. Consistently, the Post-SEP QOL scores of respondents in the four QOL domains in Figure 12 shows almost similar results. In comparison to Pre-SEP, it can be observed that there are no major changes to the respondent's Pre-SEP scores.

Figure 12. POST-SEP QOL of respondents in 4 domains

In summary there are no significant changes in the scores of the respondents QOL. However, it is good to note that there was some slight decrease in the QOL post SEP, specifically in the physical and environmental, it is inconclusive due to the lack of homogeneity of the population.

Physical Domain

It can be observed in the dumbbell dot plot presentation in Figure 13 that the physical domain QOL of the respondents have a sparse distribution. This entails that

the physical quality of life of some of the respondents decreased with most of the cases (47%) obtaining low physical QOL scores post-SEP, versus increasing (40%), while the rest (3%) remained the same. A multi-dimensional perspective study claims that it takes substantially more than physical function to adjust to stroke, further recognizing depression as the strongest predictor of QOL, along with marital status, quality of social support, and functional status, as the most important predictors of QOL of senior citizen stroke survivors (n=50) in the first three years post-discharge (Kin et al., 1999). This conclusion resonates in a quantitative study (n=1073) on the correlation of functional status and self-reported quality of life, which concludes that the QOL depends on more than just level of physical function (Samsa et al., 2004) and the observation that patients respond differently to the same disabling condition, reflecting the various ways patients adapt to similar situations. Another study says that exercise and education scheme in the community for stroke survivors showed physical and social changes, successfully improving physical integration but this was maintained in one year (Harrington, 2009) and not just within a month as what this study has conducted. Other factors common after stroke such as depression (National Stroke Association) along with reduced mobility, walking ability, reduced balance is said to have an association with lower physical activity levels (Field et al., 2013).

Figure 13. QOL: Physical domain before & after SEP

Psychological Domain

The illustration in Figure 14 shows that the majority of the respondent's psychological QOL values were above 20 prior to SEP. Intriguingly, most of the QOL values dropped below 20 after the SEP, the reason for the decrease of the scores is unknown. According to the National Stroke Association (2010), depression is an extremely common condition after a stroke. In addition to anxiety and depression that have been previously identified as determinants of QOL in patients with chronic stroke, multiple elements such as age, sex, comorbidities, stroke severity may have played a role (Li et al., 2019) as the psychological domain is affected by the characteristics associated with thinking, learning, positive and negative feelings, memory and concentration, self-esteem, body image and appearance, spirituality/religiousness/personal beliefs (Tamai et al., 2011). The improvement or non-improvement in the scores can be due to many different factors that are beyond the study limitations.

It is possible that depression and social isolation could have affected the scores

of stroke survivors. This is because the most predominantly recorded behavioral outcome of stroke is depression (Robinson et al., 1987; Sinyor et al., 1986; Wade et al., 1986, cited by Sisson 1998) and is extremely common condition after stroke (National Stroke Association, 2010). Another can be that heightened awareness of their self-aiding capacity/incapacity during the study may have affected their psychological QOL. According to Bandura, the efficacy beliefs of a person influence the magnitude of stress and depression they encounter in overcoming the demands in the environment (Bandura, 1988).

In addition, financial pressure may also affect the older adult's psychological QOL. Financial stress can be described as the psychological distress that stems from one's economic circumstances (Davis & Mantler, 2004; Davis, 2013; Drentea, 2000; Drentea & Reynolds, 2012; Dunn & Mirzaie, 2010). With 80% of them out of work and dependent mostly on their family, government support, retirement funds or savings, if any, this may also be a factor affecting them. Economic distress involves feelings that are subjective by nature and that can consist of emotions such as frustration, anger, dread, as well as fear and anxiety which limits person's ability to process thoughts with clarity, address financial pressures, and even support the living requirements (Herpolsheimer, 2012) such as their maintenance medications or nutritious food.

Figure 14. QOL: Psychological domain before & after SEP

Social Domain

The social relationships domain scores presented in Figure 15 shows that the majority of the respondents have high well distributed scores and while almost half of them appears to have increased after the SEP, several of them have also dropped, still a few remained the same. While it is said that social interaction improves QOL and decreases mortality after stroke (Venna et al.,2014), social stroke survivors often experience social isolation. The evaluation of social domain includes the facets relating to human relationships, public support and sexual activity and the data imply that the respondents have varied scores effective of the relationships acquired and the support the respondents have from others.

Human beings with personal networks are presumed to obtain greater support than those without interpersonal relationships (Elloker et al., 2011) and this is confirmed in a study with participants communicating the magnitude of assistance they

acquired from others (Beckley, 2007). In addition, it has been found to be crucial for the quality-of-life improvement of individuals after having a stroke that they keep and sustain a robust system of social support (Boden-Albala et al., 2005, Glass et al., 1992) and support from friends and family is beneficial (Sumathipala et al., 2011). Participation of respondents to stroke groups or programs created a form of support system outside their family circle that may have aided the maintenance or enhanced their social relationship scores.

Social isolation or loneliness on the other hand, in connection with widowed stroke survivors, living alone, or have separated themselves from others (or vice versa), could be factors of low social relationship scores among others. According to epidemiologic studies, loneliness was reported to be found in growing number with those who are living alone, and the aging population (Venna et al., 2016). Furthermore, social isolation poses a risk factor as well as exacerbate the consequences of cerebrovascular disease (Gaudier-Diaz et al., 2018). Surviving a stroke may be a life-long process that ultimately impacts many aspects of an individual's daily living, social relationships are of critical importance to quality of life, as it is for survival for patients after stroke (Lynch et al., 2013).

Figure 15. QOL: Social relationships domain before & after SEP

Environmental Domain

The environmental domain illustrated in Figure 16 shows environmental domain quality of life of respondents before and after SEP. While the majority of the cases have scant scores with a decreasing pattern from pre to post SEP, case number 3 noticeably have a large gap between the pre- and post-score. A study on the quality of life of elderly participants in a hospital's Geriatric Department program, that assesses the components associated with physical well-being and preservation, natural environment, economic resources, health and social services accessibility and quality, options to obtain new information and skills, participation of relaxation and transportation, have found that environment factor through their participation in group sessions was one of the predominant influence in their improvement (Tamai et al., 2011). Living accommodation, regardless of if participants live in the city or country, were found to have no impact on functional outcome, psychological outcome, and

quality of life among stroke patients in another study (Manimmanakorn et al., 2008). In another study identifying environmental influences in a stroke survivor's reengagement in important endeavors, it was revealed that among the various activities, the most important environmental influence was social support, of which majority is public and related to the system of post-stroke standard of living, which includes existence of friends and loved ones, and the quality of organization and public service delivery (Jellema et al., 2017).

Figure 16. QOL: Environmental domain before & after SEP

Table 6

Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Biophysical Profile

	Systolic Pressure	Diastolic Pressure	Mean Arterial Pressure	Heart Rate	Weight
Z Score	-.476b	-.103b	-.256b	-1.718b	-1.251b
Decision over HO	ACCEPT	ACCEPT	ACCEPT	ACCEPT	ACCEPT

Table 6 illustrates the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Biophysical Profile which answers the research question: Is there a significant difference between the biophysical profile and the QOL of older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors before and after the SEP?

The null hypothesis tested that the SEP does not improve the biophysical profile of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors, which implies that it has no significant effect. Based on analysis of data, the computed Wilcoxon statistics were converted to z-score to test the significance under normal curve. Utilizing a two-tailed test, at 0.01% level of significance, with critical values of z are -1.96 and +1.96, the obtained value of each z score did not exceed thus, this study cannot reject the null hypothesis. As such, it is determined that the SEP applied has no effect on Biophysical Profile of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors.

Table 7

Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Quality of Life

	Physical	Psychological	Social Relationships	Environmental	Q1-26
Z Score	-.035b	-.386b	.136c	-.880c	.691c
Decision over HO	ACCEPT	ACCEPT	ACCEPT	ACCEPT	ACCEPT

Table 7 shows the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Biophysical Profile which answers the research question: Is there a significant difference between the QOL of older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors before and after the SEP?

The null hypothesis tested that the SEP does not enhance the quality of life of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors, which implies that it has no significant effect. Using the same analysis technique, at 0.01% level of significance, two-tailed test, and with the same critical values of the z-score, the above obtained value of each z-score did not exceed the normal curve. Therefore, in terms of quality of life, this study cannot reject the null hypothesis. As such, it is concluded that the SEP intervention did not enhance the quality of life of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors.

QUALITATIVE DATA

Prior to the commencement of SEP and after the program, the respondents were asked to fill up a 24-hour diet and activity recall with the goal to acquire a baseline pre and post data of their diet and activity and at the same time, encourage awareness in what they were eating and/or drinking. The participants and facilitators were also interviewed post-SEP to further delve into the quality of life of older adult stroke survivors.

The interview conducted aims to gain more insights from the older adult stroke

survivors and help understand how stroke affects their quality of life using open-ended questions about their personal experience with stroke, as well as feedback on their participation in the study. Utilizing the internet and social networking platform as the medium of gathering data, the following questions were tackled:

- What challenges come to mind when you think about your lifestyle? social relationship? health management? nutrition?
- What words/feelings come to mind when you think about the program?
- How would you describe the SEP (Supportive Educative Program) in your own words?
- How was your personal experience before / during / after the program?

This chapter is the discussion of their 24 hours diet and activity recall and the major themes of the interview conducted.

Results

Analysis of the focus group discussion revealed major issues pertaining to their physical well-being and status in the environment. The following major and sub themes were classified based on the quality-of-life domains as illustrated in Table 8. It is crucial to note that the multi-dimensional nature of the quality-of-life entails that some of these themes overlap with each other.

Table 8

Themes and sub-themes of Older Adult Stroke Survivors in Various Facets of Quality of Life

Physical Health:

Activities of daily living

increased self-care management
awareness in preventive health practices
good compliance in medication
sedentary lifestyle
limited activity options
common food consumption
Go foods
Home cooked meals
Food preparation preference

Mobility

stroke adaptive functional ability

Psychological

Spirituality

strengthened spiritual practices

Personal Belief/Self Esteem

personal beliefs in quality of life

Social Relationships

Personal relationships

dependence to others

Social support

social group as means of socialization

social separation

Environment

Financial resources

poor financial capacity

inability to occupy work

Accessibility and quality of Health and social care

need for support programs

participation in stroke groups

Physical Health

As illustrated in table 5.1, the major themes discussed in the domain of physical health were under the aspects of everyday activities, movement, and ability to work of the respondents. The major themes include activities of daily living, mobility, and work capacity with the sub themes: awareness in preventive health practices, good

compliance in medications, limited activity options, Go foods, home cooked meals, food preparation preference, and stroke adaptive functional ability.

The participants talked about how important movement and the capacity to operate on a day-to-day basis and how it affects their quality of life. Most of them were able to move around with their walkers/canes independently, and while some needed assistance and supervision in performing fine motor movements, were still able to function by positive adaptation to their limitations. One respondent explained:

“Ibaiba ang kalidad ng buhay ng mga matandang nakakaligtas sa stroke un iba nasa bahay nalang hirap ng kumilos at lumakad un iba kahit paano nakakakilos”.

(Respondent 1) (“The quality of life of older stroke survivors are different for each, others have a hard time moving and walking, others somehow are able to move around”.)

According to a meta-analysis study conducted amongst stroke survivors, it was found that even to respondents who are mobile, they are unable to reach suggested degree of activities (Field et al., 2013). For those who were able to move around, they feel they were lucky to still have the freedom of mobility which others do not have.

Activities of daily living

- **Increased Self-Care Management**

One of the most prominent themes that comes up is the respondent’s increased self-care agency. Living with stroke for many years, the respondents seem to have developed and improved their skills on physical self-care through adaptation.

- **Awareness in preventive health practices**

The respondents have verbalized awareness, and their capacity to follow through with medication and diet as recommended by their providers and how they incorporate

exercise in their daily activities, signifying increased capacity of self-care. As one respondent said:

“...sa kalusugan naman dapat alam ng bawat isa sa atin ang dapat gawin at ang di dapat gawin katulad ng bisyo pagpupuyat at ang mga ipinagbabawal na kainin sa araw araw” (Respondent 3) (...in health also, every one of us should know what we need to do and not to do, like vices, staying up late and the food that is not allowed for eating every day.)

Some of the respondents also expressed incorporating learned simple and basic exercises in their activities post SEP such as stretching in the morning after waking up or upper body movement exercises while watching TV.

- **Good compliance in medications**

The participants opened their way of maintaining their health through proper diet and religiously taking their medications. A married respondent shared:

“Puro gulay, isda po pagkain namin ng mrs ko. At hindi ko po pinababayaan maintenance medicine ko”. (Respondent 5) (“My wife and I always eat vegetable and fish. Also, I don’t neglect my maintenance medication”)

After several stroke attacks, for some participants, it was necessary to make changes in their daily routinary actions for them to sustain their physical condition and maintain their sense of wellbeing. This was discussed in a similar study that concludes there is greater than just level of physical function in terms of a person’s quality of life (Samsa et al., 2004) and the observation that patients respond differently to the same disabling condition, reflecting the various ways patients adapt to similar situations.

Compliance with medications and healthy lifestyle are components of secondary prevention to stroke survivors. According to a qualitative study, in order to successfully correct the problem of non-adherence to secondary prevention medication, there is a

need for strengthening efforts to address the increasing challenges of people who survived stroke and the people taking care of them as well and enable primary care providers (Jamison et al., 2017)

Mobility

- **Stroke Adaptive Functional Ability**

The respondent's explained that they can operate every day on their own, without assistance or with the very least supervision. Evidently, the participants were able to successfully finish the study by commuting back and forth from their home to the study location. At home, they do simple household chores and activities of daily living such as dressing, bathing, cooking, and eating, all by themselves, even though it takes longer than they used to prior to their stroke. One participant said:

“Sa bahay, tumutulong ako sa paglilinis, paglalaba at pagluluto. Tinutulungan ko din yung anak kong babae sa kanyang maliit na Negosyo”. (Respondent 2) (“At home, I help in the cleaning, laundry, and cooking. I also help my daughter in her little business.”)

Another participant combined this in his daily exercise routine:

“Pagising ng umaga naglalakad-lakad ako, o nagsisimba tapos nilalakad ko lang 85alling sa bahay”. (Respondent 1) (“When I wake up in the morning I walk around, or I go to church then I just walk from the house.”)

Based on a study of older adults that are functional and their health-related quality of life measures (Godes et al., 2013), individuals who participate in some form of physical activity have a substantially better perception of their health than people who tend to spend more time inactive or just seated (Stewart et al., 1993, Rejeski et al., 1996 & 2001, Laforge et al., 1999).

- **Sedentary Lifestyle**

It is evident based on the respondent's responses in the 24-hour diet and activity assessment, that most of them were engaged in sedentary activities post meal especially after lunch. Activities such as watching TV or socializing with neighbors or friends are the common activities, they were engaged in. TV viewing is mostly the respondent's typical activity after eating meals, spending 30 minutes to 2 hours of their time.

"Pumupunta po ako sa kapitbahay at nakikipagkwentuhan". (Respondent 3) ("I go to our neighbor and talk to them")

This was consistent in the pre and post SEP as most of them were engaged in sedentary activity level. Some studies cited in Glanz (Glanz et al., 2008) have correlated certain factors in the environment that affects physical activity behavior such as access to physical activity facilities (Humpel et al., 2002) living in "walkable neighborhoods" (Saelens et al., 2003), presence of sidewalks and nearby destinations (De Bourdeaudhuij et al., 2003, Burton et al., 2005, Giles-Corti et al., 2002).

In terms of maintaining their health and adapting to their limitations, the challenges are lifestyle adjustments specifically in their activity and diet. Two of the facilitators mentioned:

"There would be drastic change when it comes to lifestyle especially when dealing with 'lifestyle change' since most stroke patients came from a phase of their life wherein, they're not physically active and have poor eating habits".

"Since they're post stroke or stroke survivors their daily activities will never be the same including food and their everyday normal routine e.g., House chores, gym workouts etc. They need to avoid strenuous activities that will trigger stress".

- **Limited Activity Options**

Since most of the respondents were not working, they stay at home practically the whole day. While they try to help as much as possible at home, there is just not enough tasks for them to do or they tire easily and thus have to rest in intervals. Watching television has become their favorite pastime. One respondent claimed:

“..eh yun lang ang libangan namin”. (Respondent 10) (“Well, that is our only hobby”).

According to a study with people with disability, not knowing where to exercise (57.9%), transportation (60.5%), lack of energy (65.8%), and cost of exercise program (84.0%) were the four highest barriers of participation in physical activity (Rimmer et al.,2000).

- **Common Food Consumption**

The 24-hour diet and activity recall shows that respondents ate more varied food coming from the 3 basic food groups available in the community. To simplify the data gathered, the researcher together with two registered dieticians classified their food intake into Go, Grow, and Glow foods: the Go-group of foods that give energy, the Grow-group of foods that build cells, and the Glow - group of food that regulates the body.

- **Go foods**

Afternoon snacks, are more common to the respondents than morning snacks, composed mainly of Go foods such as donut, biscuit, and some Glow foods for some, such as watermelon or banana. Go food is the most common food group consumed by most of the respondents which is with grow the next most shared food type, followed lastly with Glow foods. Less than half of the respondents claim they were very hungry prior to eating dinner. More than half of them said that they were not very full post dinner, rating only 3-4 over 5. Bedtime snacks is not common to 80% of the

respondents.

- **Home cooked meals**

The 24-hour diet and activity recall contain how much food the respondents ate; the estimated portion size of the serving, the preparation and the source, and the place where they bought their food if it is pre-packaged, restaurant, or fast food, as well as their activities for the day and the duration of each activity. An example of the 24hr diet and activity recall is shown on Table 9.

Table 9

24-hr diet and activity recall

Time	Type of food (eg. saging, pandesal, kape, juice, sabaw)	Quantity/Amount/Serving (eg. 1 pc, 1 baso/ta sa, 1 tbsp)	Where (eg. kusi na, canteen/cafetaria, fastfood)	Method of Preparation (eg. prito, baked, pinakuluan, fresh)	Hunger 0-5 (0-di gutom, 5-sobrang gutom)	Fullness 0-5 (0-di busog, 5-sobrang busog)	Specific Activity (eg. rehab, naglaba, naglinis ng bahay, nanood ng TV)	Duration (eg. 30 minutes, 1 hour)
8:30 am	Egg Pandesal coffee	1 pc 2 pcs 1 cup	House	Boiled Baked	5/5	4/5	Watch TV Go to market	1 hour 30min
12 noon	Banana Vegetable Rice	1 pc 1 small bowl 1 cup	House	Fresh Sauteed Steamed	4/5	5/5	Sweep floor Nap	15min 45 min
3:15 pm	<i>Toron</i> (fried banana) Orange juice candy	2 pcs s1 glass 1 pc	House	Fried Concentrated powder	3/5	4/5	Watch TV walking	1 hour 30min
7:40 pm	Fish sinigang Rice water	1 bowl 1 cup	<i>Carendaria</i>	Boiled Steamed	4/5	5/5	Wash dishes Clean kitchen	10min 15min
10:50 pm	biscuit tea	3 pcs 1 cup	<i>Sari-sari</i> store	Baked (commercial pack)	3/5	4/5	Sleep	8hours

In POST SEP, the respondent's diet and activities were relatively similar prior to the commencement of the program, eating mostly at their homes with around 13% of them eating at restaurant or the local "carenderia" and generally with sedentary activities in between major meals. Breakfast is still high with carbohydrate rich foods purchased in their respective communities.

- **Common food preparation preference**

Noticeably, mostly during lunch, it shows that respondents eat more foods coming from the 3 basic food groups compared to breakfast, with majority eating home cooked meals using boiling as the most common form of food preparation, then followed by sautéed and steamed. Southeast Asians are concerned with nutrition, economy, and ease of preparation and generally ate at home cooked meals using sautéed as most common form of preparation, followed by steaming, and lastly frying which are most common in their culinary culture (Roman et al., 2009).

The respondents are most hungry during breakfast with around 47% rated 5/5 as "very hungry" before eating while the majority rated 3, meaning they were not so hungry prior to eating. They claim to be "very full" after eating breakfast with 33% of the respondents rating 5/5 while the rest rated either 0/5 as "not full" or 3/5 "moderately full". Over the course of the study, for some reasons not covered by this research, there are more respondents eating evening snacks than morning snacks with generally similar high carbohydrate sources of food. Ideally, eating should occur when the person is not very hungry. As observed in the respondent's dinner recall, greater than half of the respondents rated 3/5 in terms of hunger before eating as well as after eating (in terms of fullness). It can also be possible that there are other reasons such as scheduled time of eating or family routine that makes them eat regardless of hunger level. However, bedtime snack is consistently not common to almost all the

respondents for some reasons not explicitly discussed by the respondents.

In Asia, dietary changes and maturing population are linked with the consistently rising cases and frequency of stroke cases (Thammaroj et al., 2005). Nonetheless, the information derived from 24-Hour Diet and Activity Recall is inconclusive and is meant mainly to provide a depiction of the respondent's diet and activities and observe modifications if any, before and after the SEP. The themes extracted from the interview are intended to explore the participant's experiences and incorporate it with the quantitative result of the study.

It was observed that despite knowing the appropriate and recommended food for them, some of them still eat their old food preferences. Also, despite knowing safe and practical exercise routines, they still fall back to their old habits. One facilitator commented:

“Nutrition has a big impact when it comes to medical management. Food has both beneficial and detrimental effects to health; therefore, nutrition care is vital to the overall intervention through modification of diet and nutrition counselling”.

Psychological

The psychological aspects of quality of life were discussed under the facets of spirituality and personal belief/self-esteem with sub themes: strengthened spiritual practices and personal beliefs in quality of life. Through prayers, the respondents verbalized being able to overcome the challenges of stroke by their belief that there is a higher being that is in control.

Spirituality

- **Strengthened Spiritual Practices**

The respondents revealed how prayers have helped them get through their stroke experience and how they incorporated their beliefs in their daily activities. Religiosity and spirituality are some of the Filipino traits that are commonly utilized by others as a powerful coping mechanism specially during sickness. The participants shared how they have incorporated this in their daily lives saying:

“Sa ngayon po active po kami sa simbahan ng asawa ko. Pinapalakas ko po ang spiritual ko hindi lang physical”. (Respondent 5) (“Right now, we are active at church with my wife. I strengthen my spiritual and not just physical.”)

It is common in numerous religious beliefs that spirituality and prayer are utilized and have become useful in getting through difficult times, hardships, and sickness. (Targ & Levine, 2002).

- **Personal Beliefs in Quality of Life**

The respondents have varied answers when asked about quality of life. Some of the respondents believe that the quality of life depends on which social status they belong to the more elevated the status in society, the more improved the quality of life they live. Some think of it in terms of their ability to move and their independence. A participant said:

While others however link it to the social status of the individual. One participant said:

“Sa kalidad ng buhay depende po sa kanilang pamumuhay kung mahirap sila o mayaman”. (Respondent 7) (“The quality of life depends on their lifestyle, whether they are poor or rich.”)

Because of this, the majority of them feel that their quality of life is just fair or

“*sakto lang*” as some of them say.)

- ***Dependence to Others***

Another recurring theme is the respondent’s dependence to other people. Because of their limitations and lack of resources, respondents were accustomed to relying on someone to meet their needs, mostly through physical assistance and/or financial support. One participant talked about her acceptance and adaptation to her limitations as a stroke survivor saying:

“Sa pamumuhay dapat ay may karamay siya sa pamumuhay di niya kakayanin ang mamuhay ng mag isa lalo na’t siya ay may karamdaman o kaya siya ay stroke na”. (Respondent 4) (“In daily living, it’s important that he/she can rely on someone, they can’t live all alone, especially if they have illness or stroke.”)

- ***Social Group as means of Socialization***

Programs conducted by various individuals or private groups which focused on the stroke survivors helped the participants through networking. One of the respondents has verbalized appreciation to the support program as their way to socialize with other people with the same condition as them and wishes there is another program or more similar program for them.

“Gusto ko un time na nagkasama kami un bonding namin kasi masaya un sya na me kwentuhan tawanan my lecture pa sana nga maulit pa” (Respondent 11) (“I like the time when we gather together, our bonding was fun, there’s storytelling, laughter and lecture as well. I hope there will be another one”)

The previous conversations of social relationships are focused on two major themes: personal relationships and social support with sub themes: dependence on others, social support as means of socialization. The respondents claim to have benefited from community programs which helped them improve their QOL. This is

consistent with the data shown previously that shows a high satisfaction score (Mean=4.133) in social QOL, particularly in personal relationships, among all other domains. The feeling of belongingness and comfort from other stroke survivors that they meet through stroke support groups and government and non-government programs they attend also helps them express their emotions and relate to other people who are in similar situations with them.

Post stroke patients must have continuity of care and must be provided with further health education for the prevention of recurrence of stroke for them to have quality of life and avoid further complications or deterioration. The respondents themselves help each other and create their own support system through sharing of resources, knowledge and assisting each other whenever they can.

Evidently, those with good social support systems were able to successfully participate in the study as they have someone to assist them for example in transportation, in using the phone, or writing down their diet or filling out forms. One of the facilitators said:

- ***Social Separation***

Respondents admitted they struggled with going back to the community and experienced feeling of abandonment specially in the beginning. The respondents also disclosed that there was a point when they withdrew themselves from the society, while others feel that it's the other way around. One participant stated that his friends, for example, seem to avoid him after he got stroke.

"Marami po akong mga kaibigan na hindi na nagpakita nung na-stroke ako".
(Respondent 4) ("I have friends who never showed up anymore after I had my stroke")

Another participant who used to be work as engineer shared that it was a way to make him see who his true friends were saying:

“Nang hindi pa po ako nastroke. Marami akong kaibigan. At marami pong lumalapit sa akin at natutulungan. Pero nang mastroke na po ako makikita mo po ang tunay mong kaibigan”. (Respondent 13) (“Before my stroke, I had many friends. Many people come to me and was helped. But when I had my stroke, I discovered who my true friends were”)

Social relationships help provide belonging and comfort. Family and relatives can help create a supportive environment in order for the patient to continuously recover even with regards to his psychological state. Meeting other people with similar conditions as them, where they can relate stories to, and share their own “stroke history” and compare their “best practices” will help them feel more connected to the community.

Environment

The key themes in the environment domain derived from the participants were aspects of accessible and quality of economic resource and health and social care. The major themes extracted were poor financial capacity, need for support programs, and participation in stroke groups. The participants verbalized concerns of not having enough programs to support stroke survivors and financial help has been scarce and limited that they believe they desperately need.

- **Poor financial resources**

Most of the participants have lost their job due to stroke disability and have since been dependent to other people’s help, financial or physical. *A respondent mentioned:*

“Mahirap ang pamumuhay ng stroke kapag kapos sa pera wala ka gamot o pangkain sa pamilya wala trabaho.” (Respondent 9) (The lifestyle of stroke is difficult if money is limited, no medication or food for the family, no work)

Programs conducted by various individuals or private groups which focused on the stroke survivors helped the participants cope with their current struggles through networking. This channels them to the right agency or source of assistance, may it be financial, moral/social, spiritual support. Meeting other people of similar conditions and through open discussions of their health issues gives them hope, and through their sharing of experiences and best practices, provides them the emotional and social support that they need to move forward. Some of the respondents expressed the importance of active participation in the society, and despite their disability they try to reach out to available resources in the community.

- **Inability to Occupy Work**

The socioeconomic status which is considered an important determinant of quality of life of participants, were usually tackled in the area of the respondent's ability to occupy work. However, due to their physical limitations, most of the respondents have lost their job when they had their stroke. They talked about how difficult it is for them to earn a living. Most of them are forced to rely on their spouse and/or children for support, and social services. One participant who used to be a head of an office said,

“Mahirap po kasi walang trabaho, nasa bahay lang at walang income”.

(Respondent 1) (It's difficult to have no work and have no income.)

The limitations on their previous abilities because of their stroke have cost them to lose their job and in consequence, affected their ability to earn a living for themselves and their family. The restrictions of motor and cognitive abilities as part of neurological impairment in stroke is often abrupt or unpredictable and such impairments can impede the individual's 'abilities' to socialize or maintain employment (Dixon, 2007) such as getting to work using the public transportation, and the

communication challenges as well while some of them are still under physical or speech therapy.

It is not new that there are certain limitations that are evident in the participants and one of the facilitators talked about the stroke survivor's need for assistance and supervision:

Since they're post stroke or stroke survivors their day-to-day activities will never be the same including food and their everyday normal routine e.g. House chores, exercises etc. They need to avoid strenuous activities that will trigger stress.

- ***Need for Support Programs***

Most of the participants feel that there were not enough programs by the government that help attend to their needs such as financial aid, medical, or support programs that will improve their quality of life. Although some private organizations have helped take care of some of their basic needs, such as free diagnostics and medications through medical outreach programs, they were not enough and not as often to meet their needs. According to one of the respondents, they need more programs that cares for stroke patients:

"Magkaroon ng mas matibay at matatag na programa na makakatulong para sa aming mga stroke patient upang mapalago ang kaalaman sa aming kasalukuyang estado sa buhay". (Respondent 8) (Have durable and stable programs that will help us, stroke patients, so we can grow our knowledge in our current state of life.)

Another commented:

"..magkaroon ng sapat, produktibong at progresibong programa na tutugon at kakalinga sa aming mga stroke". (Respondent 13) (..have enough, productive, and progressive programs that will address and care for us, stroke.)

Support programs help stroke survivors not only materially but also in learning

new things and gaining more information about their health that provides a positive feeling and boosts their self-esteem. Applying the lessons, they learn from the programs in their daily life helps increase their self-confidence and decreases their dependence on other people. A longitudinal investigation involving 63 respondents discovered there was a powerful association between a person's quality of life and that heightened self-efficacy after stroke (Jones, 2010). Stroke support programs provides them a safe avenue for learning useful techniques, by introducing safe exercise routines the participants can perform based on their physical limitations as well as dietary recommendations to refresh their memory on the importance of eating healthy and choosing the right kinds of food to control hypertension, maintain ideal body weight, and reduce risk of recurrence that are essential in stroke management and prevention.

- ***Participation in Support Groups***

For some of the participants, it is helpful to have a support system outside their homes through stroke programs. The stroke support group, for example, where some of the participants are active members, are beneficial to them in terms of connecting back to the society through organized programs and by meeting other people who are relatable and supportive of their struggles and/or experiences as stroke survivors. According to one participant:

“Thankful nga ako na nagkaroon ng program na nagkasama kami no dull moments each day is a waiting day na pumunta at makinig”. (Respondent 1) (I’m thankful there is a program where we can be together, no dull moments each day is a waiting day to go and listen.)

Despite their disability and status, the participants were able to keep a positive disposition and show willingness to participate and learn new things. As the facilitators

described the participants:

“They are very cooperative and attentive and are eager to learn and are participative. You can see their enthusiasm towards the program”.

The respondents were observed willing to take up the challenge of the program’s activities such as the stroke adaptive exercises taught and the diet recall.

Vicarious experience is learned and can be observed from other people, which can be beneficial to certain individuals. This is gained through the evaluation and demonstration of others, and this is usually obtained by witnessing a person effectively execute a task or listening from other people’s experiences of the recovery period post stroke (Jones et al., 2010).

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The study integrated Dorothea Orem's self-care deficit concept employing the mixed methods explanatory sequential design to determine the effects of supportive-educative program (SEP) to the QOL of older adult stroke survivors. The salient findings of this investigation were the following:

1. The mean age of the study population was from the middle-old, aged group (70-80), majority of which were male (60 %) with female (40 %). Most of the respondents were married (53.33%), while the rest were already widowed (20%), single (13.33%), in a relationship (6.66%), or separated (6.66%).

2. In general, the respondents were highly educated: college graduate (53%), but currently non-working (80%), financially dependent on their pension (40%), their spouse or children (13%) or both, while only 6% have a business income source.

3. Overall data implies that out of 15 respondents there were positive improvements in SBP in 7 out of 15 cases (46.66%), DBP in 5 out of 15 cases (33.33%), MAP in 6 out of 15 cases (40%). There was no change in weight, only 8 out of 15 cases (53.33%) had ± 0.206 kilograms difference post-SEP.

4. The quality-of-life score was discovered low in Psychological domain crediting on the negative feelings in appearance and self-esteem and high in the areas of Physical and Social indicating positive coping in activities of daily living and personal relationships.

5. The physical domain quality of life data shows an average perception before (mean=3.504) and after SEP (mean=3.152) with a standard deviation of $sd < 1$

prior to SEP implying that the respondent's scores vary from one another in a high extent and is expected.

6. Among the 4 domains, psychological QOL scored the lowest, followed by the environmental. The respondent's psychological quality of life perception data shows a pre-SEP mean=3.244 to slightly below average post-SEP mean=2.966 with a standard deviation of 0.7921 and 0.8950 respectively. This implies that the respondent's perception of their psychological QOL is neither high nor low and their perception slightly changed even lower after the program.

7. The social domain is the most constant among the 4 domains of QOL, with a standard deviation of $sd=0.6359$ (mean=3.399) almost identical before and after the program $sd= 0.6048$ (mean=3.444) suggesting a constant social QOL among respondents, consistent with the positive personal relationships and social support feedback during the interview with the respondents. Moreover, the respondents have the highest satisfaction (mean=4.133) in their personal relationships under the social domain which is also the highest mean score among other questions in all domains.

8. The major themes derived from the focus group discussion were day to day activities, mobility, and work capacity, with the sub themes: awareness in preventive health practices, good compliance in medications, limited activity options, Go foods, home cooked meals, food preparation preference, stroke adaptive functional ability and inability to occupy work.

9. Based on analysis of data, the computed Wilcoxon statistics were converted to z-score to test the significance under normal curve. The critical values of z are -1.96 and +1.96 at 0.01% level of significance and two-tailed test, of which basis this study cannot reject the null hypothesis since the obtained value of each z score did not exceed these values. As such, it is concluded that the SEP conducted has no

significant effect on the Biophysical Profile of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors. There is no significant difference between the biophysical profile and the QOL of older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors before and after the SEP.

Conclusion

In this study, the respondents mean age was from the middle-old, aged group (70-80), majority of which were male (60 %), married (53.33%) or widowed (20%), highly educated (college graduate=53%) and are unemployed (80%), financially dependent on their pension (40%), or their spouse/children (13%).

Based on the analysis of data, it is concluded that the SEP has no significant effect on biophysical profile of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors and there is no significant difference between the biophysical profile before and after the SEP. Overall data implies that out of 15 respondents there were minimal positive improvements in SBP (7 out of 15 cases or 46.66%), DBP (5 out of 15 cases or 33.33%), MAP (6 out of 15 cases or 40%), with only ± 0.206 kilograms difference in 8 out of 15 cases post-SEP.

Furthermore, QOL score was found low in Psychological domain, followed by the environmental, reflecting on negative feelings in appearance and self-esteem and was found high in Physical and Social domains indicating positive coping in activities of daily living and personal relationships. Some of the major themes identified by the participants in no particular order were: increased self-care management, sedentary lifestyle, strengthened spiritual practices, dependence on others, and social support. Sub themes include stroke adaptive functional ability, limited activity options, Go foods, home cooked meals, and food preparation preference. The drop in psychological domain could be related to depression or financial stress. While the

increase in social domain can be attributed to their continued participation in community activities and strong family support.

Moreover, sedentary lifestyle appears to be evident in most, if not all respondents. Common activities in the morning include household chores such as cleaning, washing dishes, sweeping, watching television, and talking with neighbors classified as light physical activities. Based on the data gathered, most of the respondents eat at their home and cook their food fried in major meals specially during breakfast or boiled and steamed in other major meals. Majority eat carbohydrate rich foods with rice groups as the leading most consumed food group, followed by protein rich food particularly in large meals which includes breakfast, lunch, and dinner.

Additionally, the focus group data suggests that the participants value their mobility, as well as ability to accomplish their everyday tasks and were able to positively adapt to their limitations along with strengthened spiritual beliefs and strong social support coming from family and stroke support group. However, sedentary lifestyle, poor financial resources, inability to occupy work, and dependence on others continues to be their burden. Generally, the respondents know the importance of proper nutrition and regular eating habits with preference in boiled, sautéed, and steamed food that are available in the community.

In conclusion, SEP has no significant effect on Biophysical Profile of the older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors and no significant difference were found between the biophysical profile and the QOL of older adult post-cerebral stroke survivors before and after the SEP. Although it is impossible to assume that the study population is representative of the target population in this study, valuable information derived from the available data was extracted for future research endeavors. In scientific literature, both positive and negative findings are invaluable as they influence us to appraise and

substantiate our current ideas. Fundamentally, this process of constant evaluation and validation of existing information push us towards unabridged science (Matosin et al., 2014).

Recommendations

Future research studies should address the limitations discussed in this study. Subsequent researchers may focus on effective and efficient methods to obtain larger samples such as utilizing multiple methods for gathering participants. It is advisable to anchor on established clubs and support groups existing in the community as they are already organized and well established. Combining multiple methods that are more efficacious in gathering more robust respondents is critical to have good representation of the population. Alternatively, conducting the program in their preferred environment such as in their own house, their club meeting place or within the barangay may also limit hesitations and promote more participation from the target population. This however may need more time, funds, and resources.

Also, recruiting a larger population with less highly selected samples can derive a more generalizable result for the older population. Chi-square tests may be used to determine significant relationships between the two variables and ANOVA for two or more groups. The data treatment presented in this study, Wilcoxon signed rank test, was utilized due to the small sample size (Sawilowsky & Blair, 1992) and consideration of the limitations of the study. However, t-test is more powerful when the population is normally distributed (Conover, 1992).

Additionally, safety measures that are well established can be placed to properly address concerns for older adult stroke survivors in order to include populations that are equally capable of performing and participating in the activities of the program but

with more complicated cases or more comorbidities will help make the study less more conservative and more inclusive.

Furthermore, it would be beneficial to obtain additional information in common comorbidities that may also be useful in establishing connections and may help in forming insightful conclusions. Gathering more health history background information will help gain a detailed and more holistic view of the respondent's medical health which are usually interrelated. Risk factor management is one of the keys to stroke prevention and comorbidities increase the risk factors. This may require a more complex data management.

Another possible improvement would be to utilize a different type of research such as experimental. Quasi-experimental are not as compelling as experimental research in establishing causal connections between interventions and outcomes. Thus, given a longer time frame and good research funding, this may be conducted to a more specific and wide number of respondents.

The 24-Hour Diet and Activity Recall activity was meant to record everything the respondents eat or drink with the intention to derive insights of the respondent's nutrition status as part of their quality of life. However, this poses a challenge for some of the respondents that required assistance in writing due to fine motor limitations or memory limitations. Thus, involving their significant others in the assessment can also be explored.

The following are the specific recommendations of the researcher to the stakeholders of the study:

Patient and Family - The accuracy of data information depends on answers and feedback of patients. It is imperative that if there are any difficulties in answering the questionnaires due to loss of fine motor skills or physical impediment that patients

seek assistance. A successful lifestyle modification (and hypertension prevention and control) requires high level knowledge, social support and practice. Partnering with others or bringing significant person may help make the job easier. Health promotion is not just an individual battle but a team effort. The more people get involved, the better the outcome.

Also, stroke education program can be modified to a span of three to six months, with proper funding and support from key players in the community. It is not just cognizance and understanding of secondary prevention that is vital but the application of the concepts and lifestyle modification that stroke survivors and their family can truly benefits from its effects, which includes strengthening their skills and capabilities among others, and ultimately impact their quality of life in the long run, through regular active lifestyle, and mental health.

Nurse - Numerous insights can be derived from this study, from recruitment, data gathering, to analysis, future nurse researchers modify the study to fit their particular interest in health promotion, stroke survivors, and even community nursing. It is advisable to expand the number of respondents and not merely focusing on the older adults to create a more generalizable study. As stroke is becoming common in varied lifespan, is possible to explore the effects of health promotion programs in other age groups. Although it is uncertain why psychological QOL scored the lowest amongst the 4 domains, it is perhaps good to explore this area further. Additionally, the qualitative data can be strengthened by using different techniques and combining multiple methods to saturate the data information needed to make a concrete generalization. Nurses play a vital role in public health and this study would make an impact to post-stroke survivors living in the community, if carried out correctly and effectively. The barangay health centers, and community leaders play a key role in

implementing any health programs and is important to gain their respect, cooperation and to work with them closely.

Nursing practice - There are various theories and concepts that can be applied in health promotion programs for other chronic illnesses that need self-care and continuity of care. Nurses can develop new measures and test interventions utilizing the information provided in this study to improve the quality of life of stroke survivors during or post hospitalization. People with disability, and chronic health conditions that need secondary prevention are as crucial as much as those who are actively admitted in the hospital and on a sick role. Nurses should discover the various possibilities in this area to help improve or maintain the quality of life. It has been previously established that prevention is the most pertinent and inexpensive part of our expertise yet, prevention is often overlooked (Stroke Society of the Philippines, 2006).

Research- Geriatric populations can be challenging due to its nature of complexity and multiple considerations, but with knowledge, dedication, right people, and enough resources, it can be very rewarding and satisfying. The writer recommends future researcher studies to put emphasis on the needs of older adults' stroke survivors in other aspects: acute, convalescent, recovery phase, and secondary prevention. To explore geriatric communities in barangays, especially those who will profit greatly on secondary prevention and self-care management.

Another would be to delve deeper into their biophysical profile and the factors that affect/not affect their quality of life. The psychological followed by the environmental respectively, where the two lowest scores among the four domains, as well as the social domain where the highest scores were derived, are points of interests that are worth further exploration.

Future research studies should focus on the constraints discussed in this study

so as to create a homogenous population to make the data generalizable to the post-cerebrovascular stroke older adult population. As cerebrovascular cases affect more and more younger generations, it is also possible to extend the research to the adult group or younger population to gather and accommodate more participants to produce a generalizable inference and assumptions of the quality of life of stroke survivors.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Letter of Permission

To : **TELESFORO E. GANA, JR., MD**
Medical Director
ManilaMed (Medical Center Manila)

Thru : **Mr. Jose Ronaldo Delos Santos**
Chief Operations Officer
ManilaMed (Medical Center Manila)

Anthony Martin S. Dolor M.D.
Operations Group Head
ManilaMed (Medical Center Manila)

Dear Dr.Gana/Sir,

I am Alana Aissa Gem B. Barias, currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing major in Adult Health Nursing at the University of the Philippines Open University. In the pursuit of knowledge and its contribution to healthcare and nursing profession, I am presently making my research study with the title “Supportive-Educative Program on the Quality of Life of Older Adult Post-Cerebral Stroke Survivors”. In line with this purpose, it is my great privilege to ask permission to conduct the study in your institution. This is an interventional study with an aim to provide a health promotion program for stroke patients. The undersigned researcher would be more than willing to discuss further the specifics of the study. Ethical considerations and research principles shall be adhered.

May this letter merit your kind approval.

Sincerely,

ALANA AISSA GEM B.BARIAS, RN
Researcher

Noted by:

QUEENIE R. REDULME, RN, MAN
Research Mentor and Associate Professor
University of the Philippines Open University

October 26, 2015

To : **ELIZABETH LATHROP CAPAPAS**
Barangay Chairman
Barangay 695, Zone 75
District V-Manila, National Capital Region

Dear Ma'am:

I am Alana Aissa Gem B. Barias, a registered nurse, currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing, major in Adult Health at the University of the Philippines Open University. In the pursuit of knowledge and its contribution to healthcare and nursing profession, I am presently making my research study with the title "Supportive-Educative Program on the Quality of Life of Older Adult Post-Cerebral Stroke Survivors".

In line with this purpose, it is my great privilege to ask permission to conduct a supportive-educative session in your Barangay Center, for 60 minutes (9am-10am) every Tuesdays, Thursdays, and Saturdays in the month of January-February. This is an interventional study with an aim to provide a health promotion program for stroke survivors. The undersigned researcher would be more than willing to discuss further the specifics of the study. Ethical considerations and research principles shall be adhered.

May this letter merit your kind approval.

Sincerely,

ALANA AISSA GEM B.BARIAS, RN
Researcher
Contact No: 09192991882
Email: bariasalana@yahoo.com

Noted by:

QUEENIE R. REDULME, RN, MAN
Research Mentor and Associate Professor
University of the Philippines Open University

October 26, 2015

To : **HON. DANTE B. GONZALO**
Barangay Chairman
Barangay 670, Zone 72
District V-Manila, National Capital Region

Dear Sir:

I am Alana Aissa Gem B. Barias, a registered nurse, currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing, major in Adult Health at the University of the Philippines Open University. In the pursuit of knowledge and its contribution to healthcare and nursing profession, I am presently making my research study with the title "Supportive-Educative Program on the Quality of Life of Older Adult Post-Cerebral Stroke Survivors".

In line with this purpose, it is my great privilege to ask permission to conduct a supportive-educative session in your Barangay Center, for 60 minutes (9am-10am) every Tuesdays, Thursdays, and Saturdays in the month of January-February. This is an interventional study with an aim to provide a health promotion program for stroke survivors. The undersigned researcher would be more than willing to discuss further the specifics of the study. Ethical considerations and research principles shall be adhered.

May this letter merit your kind approval.

Sincerely,

ALANA AISSA GEM B.BARIAS, RN
Researcher
Contact No: 09192991882
Email: bariasalana@yahoo.com

Noted by:

QUEENIE R. REDULME, RN, MAN
Research Mentor and Associate Professor
University of the Philippines Open University

October 26, 2015

ARNOLD M.PANGAN, MD

Office in Charge
Director, Manila Department of Social Welfare
Manila City Hall

Dear Dr.Pangan,

I am Alana Aissa Gem B. Barias, currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing major in Adult Health Nursing at the University of the Philippines Open University. In the pursuit of knowledge and its contribution to healthcare and nursing profession, I am presently making my research study with the title “Supportive-Educative Program on the Quality of Life of Older Adult Post-Cerebral Stroke Survivors”.

In line with this purpose, it is my great privilege to ask permission to conduct the study in the senior citizens of Manila. It is my intention to ask for an access to possible respondents from your office. This is an interventional study with an aim to provide a Supportive-Educative Program for stoke survivors. The undersigned researcher would be more than willing to discuss further the specifics of the study. Ethical considerations and research principles shall be adhered.

May this letter merit your kind approval.

Sincerely,

ALANA AISSA GEM B.BARIAS, RN
Researcher

Appendix B

Author's Approval to Use and Translate QOL Questionnaire

To: The World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL)- BREF
Publications Email: permission@who.int

Dear Ma'am/Sir:

I am Alana Aissa Gem B. Barias, currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing major in Adult Health Nursing at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am presently making my research study with the title "Supportive-Educative Program on the Quality of Life of Older Adult Post-Cerebral Stroke Survivors". In line with this, I would like to ask permission to use the tool WHOQOL-BREF and translate it from English to Tagalog, the national language of the Philippines. This is an interventional study with an aim to provide a Supportive-Educative Program for stroke patients benefit. Ethical considerations and research principles shall be adhered. I am looking forward for your approval.

Respectfully yours,
Alana Aissa Gem Barias

● Permission to use the WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire (2) People ★

● **Alana Barias** Dear Ma'am/Sir: Good day! I am Alana Aissa Gem B. Barias, currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing major in Adl Sep 9 at 4:53 PM ★

● **whoqol** <whoqol@who.int>
To: Alana Barias 📧 Sep 16 at 9:50 PM ★

Dear Alana,

Thank you for your interest in the WHOQOL-BREF. Please fill in the attached user-agreement form and return a signed copy to me by email; I will then send you the Filipino version of the questionnaire, free-of charge.

Best regards,

Sibel
Mrs Sibel Volkan
Health Statistics and Information Systems (HSI)
The World Health Organization
20 Avenue Appia
CH-1211 Geneva 27
Switzerland

> Show original message

[WHOQOL_BREF_Us....pdf](#)

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Appendix C
Research Questionnaires

WHO-BREF Questionnaire

*The following questions ask how you feel about your quality of life, health, or other areas of your life. I will read out each question to you, along with the response options. **Please choose the answer that appears most appropriate.** If you are unsure about which response to give to a question, the first response you think of is often the best one.*

*Please keep in mind your standards, hopes, pleasures and concerns. We ask that you think about your life **in the last four weeks.***

	<i>Very Poor</i>	<i>Poor</i>	<i>Neither poor nor good</i>	<i>Good</i>	<i>Very good</i>
	1	2	3	4	5
1. How would you rate your quality of life?					
	1	2	3	4	5
2. How satisfied are you with your health					
The following questions ask about how much you have experienced certain things in the last four weeks.					
	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>A little</i>	<i>A moderate amount</i>	<i>Very much</i>	<i>An extreme amount</i>
	5	4	3	2	1
3. To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?					
4. How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?					
	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>A little</i>	<i>A moderate amount</i>	<i>Very much</i>	<i>An extreme amount</i>
	1	2	3	4	5
5. How much do you enjoy life?					
6. To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?					
	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>A little</i>	<i>A moderate amount</i>	<i>Very much</i>	<i>Extremely</i>
	1	2	3	4	5
7. How well are you able to concentrate					
8. How do you feel in your daily life?					

9. How healthy is your physical environment					
The following questions ask about how completely you experience or were able to certain things in the last four weeks.					
	Not at all	A little	Moderately	Mostly	Completely
	1	2	3	4	5
10. Do you have enough energy for everyday life?					
11. Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?					
12. Have you enough money to meet your needs?					
13. How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?					
14. To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?					
15. How well are you able to get around?					
	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied
	1	2	3	4	5
16. How satisfied are you with your sleep?					
17. How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily activities?					
18. How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?					
19. How satisfied are you with yourself?					
20. How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?					
21. How satisfied are you with your sex life?					
22. How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?					
23. How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?					
24. How satisfied are you with your access to health services?					
25. How satisfied are you with your transport?					
The following question refers to how often you have felt or experienced certain things in the last four weeks					
	Never	Seldom	Quite often	Very often	Always
	5	4	3	2	1
26. How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression?					
Do you have any comments about the assessment?					

The following table should be completed after the interview is finished					
		Equations for computing domain scores	Raw score	Transformed scores*	
				4-20	0-100
27	Domain 1	$(6-Q3)+(6-Q4)+Q10+Q15+Q16+Q17+Q18$	a.=	b:	c:
28	Domain 2	$Q5+Q6+Q7+Q11+Q19+(6-Q26)$	a.=	b:	c:
29	Domain 3	$Q20+Q21+Q22$	a.=	b:	c:
30	Domain 4	$Q8+Q9+Q12+Q13+Q14+Q23+Q24+Q25$	a.=	b:	c:

The Barthel Index

Patient Name:

Rater Name:

Date:

Activity

Score

FEEDING

0=unable

5=needs help cutting, spreading butter, etc. or requires modified diet

10=independent

BATHING

0= dependent

5=independent (or in shower)

GROOMING

0=needs to help with personal care

5=independent face/hair/teeth/shaving (implements provided)

DRESSING

0=dependent

5=needs help but can do about half unaided

10=independent (including buttons, zips, laces, etc.)

BOWELS

0=incontinent (or needs to be given enemas)

5=occasional accident

BLADDER

0-incontinent, or catheterized and unable to manage alone

5= occasional accident

10=continent

TOILET USE

0=dependent

5=needs some help, but can do something alone

10=independent (on and off, dressing, wiping)

TRANSFERS (BED TO CHAIR AND BACK)

0=unable, no sitting balance

5=needs some help (one or two people, physical) can sit

10=minor help (verbal or physical)

15=independent

MOBILITY (ON LEVEL SURFACES)

- 0=immobile or <50yards
- 5=wheelchair independent, including concerns, >50 yards
- 10=walks with help of one person (verbal or physical) >50 yards
- 15=independent (but may use any aid; for example, stick) >50 yards

yards

STAIRS

- 0=unable
- 5=needs help (verbal, physical, carrying aid)
- 10=independent

The Barthel ADL Index Guidelines:

The index should be used as a record of what a patient does, not as a record of what a patient could do.

The main aim is to establish degree of independence from any help, physical or verbal, however minor and for whatever reason.

The need for supervision renders the patient not independent.

A patient's performance should be established using the best available evidence. Asking the patient, friends/relatives and nurses are the usual sources, but direct observation and common sense are also important. However direct testing is not needed.

Usually the patient's performance over the preceding 24-48 hours is important, but occasionally longer periods will be relevant.

Middle categories imply that the patient supplies over 50 per cent of the effort.

Use of the aids to be independent is allowed

Demographic Data Sheet

Respondent's Code: Accomplished:	Date
<p>Age: _____</p> <p>Sex: <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female</p> <p>Civil Status:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Single</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Married</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Separated/Divorced</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Widowed</p> <p>Accompanied by:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>Relationship to Patient:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Family Member</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">Specify: _____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Relatives</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other</p>	<p>Educational Attainment:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> College Graduate <input type="checkbox"/> College Level</p> <p>Course: _____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Vocation/ Technical Course</p> <p>Course: _____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> High School Graduate <input type="checkbox"/> High School Level</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Elementary Graduate <input type="checkbox"/> Elementary Level</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No Formal Education</p>

Biophysical Data Sheet

Respondent s Code	Weight		BP	MAP	HR
	Before	After			

Appendix D

Tagalog WHO-BREF Questionnaire

I.D. No. _____

TUNGKOL SA IYO

Bago po tayo magsimula, nais po naming sagutin ninyo ang ilang katanungan tungkol sa inyong sarili. Bilugan po ninyo ang pinaka-angkop na sagot o isulat sa puwang / espasyo.

Ano po ang inyong kasarian? Lalaki Babae

Kailan po kayo ipinanganak (birthday)? _____
Araw Buwan Taon

Hanggang saan po ang inyong natapos sa pag-aaral?

Walang natapos	Walang natapos High School (Year Level _____)	Vocational _____
Elementarya (Grade Level _____)	Kolehiyo (Year level _____)	Iba pa _____

Kayo po ba ay may asawa?

Walang asawa	May asawa pero hindi kasal	Biyuda/Biyudo
Kasal /May asawa	Hivalay	

Kayo po ba ay may trabaho o regular na gawa? OO _____ Wala _____
Ano po ang inyong trabaho o regular na Gawain? _____

Saan po kayo kumukuha ng inyong pangastos?

Sa pension	Galing sa asawa	Galing sa apo
Sa inipon na perang pansarili	Galing sa anak	Iba pa

Kayo po ba ay miyembro ng grupo ng Senior Citizen ? OO _____
HINDI _____

Pangalan ng Grupo ng Senior Citizen _____

Kayo po ba ay may Senior Citizen Card? OO _____ WALA _____

May sakit / karamdaman po ba kayo ngayon?

OO/ may sakit _____ HINDI/Walang sakit _____ May sakit pero normal ang pakiramdam _____

Kung masama ang inyong pakiramdam, ano kaya ito sa inyong palagay?

Mataas ang presyon	Sakit sa puso	Sakit sa baga
Diabetes	Atake sa utak	Iba pa

Mga Instruksyon/Alituntunin

Ang mga sumusunod na tanong ay tungkol sa inyong mga pakiramdam, kalidad ng inyong buhay, kalusugan, o iba pang aspeto ng inyong buhay. Pakisagot po ang lahat ng mga tanong. Kung hindi po kayo sigurado sa inyong sagot, piliin po lamang ang sa tingin ninyo ang siyang pinaka-angkop. Kadalasan, ito ang unang sagot na naisip ninyo.

Isipin po ninyong mabuti ang inyong mga pamantayan (standards), pangarap, kasiyahan at mga problema sa buhay. Isipin po ninyo ang inyong buhay nitong nakalipas na dalawang linggo. Halimbawa, habang iniisip ang mga nangyari sa inyo nitong nakalipas na dalawang linggo, kayo ay tatanungin ng ganito:

Nakukuha niyo ba mula sa ibang tao ang tulong o suporta na kailangan ninyo?	Hindi kailanman	Hindi gaano	Katamtaman	Marami	Kompleto
	1	2	3	4	5

Bilugan ang numero na nagsasaad kung gaanoong tulong o suporta ang nakuha ninyo mula sa ibang tao, nitong nakalipas na dalawang linggo. Inyong bibilugan and numerong 4 kung maraming suporta ang nakuha ninyo mula sa ibang tao, katulad ng ganito:

Nakukuha niyo ba mula sa ibang tao ang tulong o suporta na kailangan ninyo?	Hindi kailanman	Hindi gaano	Katamtaman	Marami	Kompleto
	1	2	3	4	5

Bilugan ang numero 1 kung hindi ka kailanman nakatanggap ng suporta o tulong mula sa ibang tao nitong nakalipas na dalawang linggo.

Basahin po ang bawat tanong, suriin ang inyong nararamdaman, at bilugan ang numero na nagsasaad ng inyong pinaka-angkop na sagot sa bawat tanong.

		Lubhang Hindi Kontento	Hindi Kontento	Medyo Kontento (OK lang)	Kontento	Sobrang Kontento
1 (6,1)	1. Gaano kayo ka kontento sa kalidad ng inyong buhay	1	2	3	4	5

		Lubhang Hindi Kontento	Hindi Kontento	Medyo Kontento (OK lang)	Kontento	Sobrang Kontento
2 (64)	2. Gaanopo kayo ka kontento sa inyong kalusugan?	1	2	3	4	5

Ang mga sumusunod ay tungkol sa kung **gaano mo naranasan** ang mga bagay-
bagay nitong **nakaraang dalawang linggo**.

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo:	Hindi Naranasan	Naranasan nang Konti/Bahagya	Naranasan	Naranasang Madalas	Lubhang Madalas na Naranasan
3 (F1.4)	3. Gaano mo naranasan na ang pananakit ng katawan ay naging sagabal sa iyong mga pang-araw-araw na gawain	1	2	3	4	5
4 (F11.3)	4. Gaano niyo kinailangan ang magpagamot, upang inyong magampanan ang pang-araw-araw na gawain?	1	2	3	4	5
5 (F4.1)	5. Gaano niyo naranasan ang kasiyahan (enjoy) sa inyong buhay?	1	2	3	4	5
6 (F24.2)	6. Gaano niyo naranasan na may saysay o kabuluhan ang inyong buhay?	1	2	3	4	5

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo	Lubhang Walang Kakayahan/Hinding hindi	Konti	Medyo	May kakayahan/nararamdaman	Mahusay na kakayahan at nararamdaman
7 (F5.3)	7. Gaano ang iyong kakayahang magconcentrate?	1	2	3	4	5
8 (F16.1)	8. Gaano niyo naramdaman na ikaw ay ligtas sa anumang kapahamakan sa inyong pang-araw-araw na buhay?	1	2	3	4	5
9 (F22.1)	9. Gaano kalusog at ligtas sa sakit ang inyong paligid?	1	2	3	4	5

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo	Walang-wala / Hinding-hindi	Konti at Hindi Sapat	Medyo Sapat	Sapat/Madalas/ Tanggap	Laging Sapat/ Laging Tanggap
10 (F2.1)	10. May sapat ka bang lakas para sa pang-araw-araw na gawain?	1	2	3	4	5
11 (F7.1)	11. Tanggap ba ninyo ang iyong pisikal na anyo o pangangatawan?	1	2	3	4	5
12 (F18.1)	12. May sapat ka bang pera para sa iyong mga pangangailangan?	1	2	3	4	5

13 (F20.1)	13. Gaano mo kadalang makuha ang mga kailangan niyong impormasyon mula sa radio, tv, diyario atbp., sa iyong pang-arawaraw na buhay?	1	2	3	4	5
14 (F21.1)	14. Gaano kadalang ang inyong pagkakataon at oras para sa paglilibang o kasiyahan?	1	2	3	4	5

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo	Lubhang walang kakayahang	Walang Kakayahang	Medyo may Kakayahang	May Kakayahang	Mahusay ang Kakayahang
15 (F9.1)	15. Gaano ang iyong kakayahang magpunta sa mga lugar na gusto mong puntahan?	1	2	3	4	5

Ang sumusunod na katanungan ay tungkol sa kung gaano ka kakontento sa iba't ibang aspeto ng inyong buhay nitong mga **nakaraang dalawang linggo**.

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo	Lubhang Hindi Kontento Hindi	Hindi Kontento	Medyo Kontento	Kontento	Laging Kontento
16 (F13.1)	16. Gaano kayo kakontento sa inyong pagtulog?	1	2	3	4	5
17 (F20.3)	17. Gaano kayo kakontento sa iyong kakayahang gawin ang mga pang-arawaraw mong gawain?	1	2	3	4	5
18 (F12.4)	18. Gaano ka kakontento sa iyong kakayahang gumawa o magtrabaho ?	1	2	3	4	5
19 (F6.3)	19. Gaano ka kakontento sa iyong sarili?	1	2	3	4	5

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo	Lubhang Hindi Kontento	Hindi Kontento	Medyo Kontento	Kontento	Laging Kontento
20 (F13.3)	20. Gaano ka kakontento sa inyong mga personal na relasyon (halimbawa, sa Diyos, sa pamilya at kaibigan ?	1	2	3	4	5
21 (F15.3)	21. Gaano ka kakontento sa inyong seksual na buhay?	1	2	3	4	5
22 (F14.4)	22. Gaano ka kakontento sa suporta na nakukuha mo mula sa iyong mga kaibigan?	1	2	3	4	5

23 (F17.3)	23. Gaano ka kakontento sa kalagayan ng iyong tirahan?	1	2	3	4	5
------------	--	---	---	---	---	---

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo	Lubhang Hindi Kontento	Hindi Kontento	Medyo Kontento	Kontento	Laging Kontento
24 (F19.3)	24. Gaano ka kakontento sa iyong kakayahang makakuha ng serbisyong pangkalusugan mula sa guberno o sa pribadong serbisyo?	1	2	3	4	5
25 (F23.3)	25. Kontento ka ba sa iyong kakayahang upang makamit ang paraan ng transportasyon	1	2	3	4	5

Ang sumusunod ay tungkol sa kung **gaano mo kadalang** naramdaman o naranasan ang mga ito nitong

nakaraang dalawang linggo.

	Nakaraang dalawang linggo.	Hinding hindi naranasan	Bihira/Medyo Naranasan	Madalas Naranasan	Sobrang Madalas Naranasan	Palaging Naranasan
26 (F8.1)	26. Gaano niyo kadalang naranasan ang mga hindi magagandang damdamin tulad ng pagsumpung, pagkabigo, pagkabahala at sobrang kalungkutan at lumbay?	1	2	3	4	5
		Lubhang Hindi Kontento	Hindi Kontento	Medyo Kontento (OK lang)	Kontento	Sobrang Kontento
27.	4. Gaano kayo ka kontento sa ganda ng inyong buhay?	1	2	3	4	5

Anu-ano ang mga bagay na makakadagdag ng kalidad sa inyong buhay?

Paano sa inyong palagay, maitataas ang kalidad ng inyong buhay?

Mayroon po bang tumulong sa iyo sa pag-sagot ng mga katanungang ito?
OO _____ HINDI _____

Gaano katagal mong natapos ang pagsagot sa mga katanungan? _____ minuto

Mayroon po ba kayong katanungan o mungkahi tungkol sa mga katanungang ito?

Appendix E

3-Day Diet and Activity Recall

3-DAY DIET and ACTIVITY RECALL

Pangalan: _____ Edad: _____ Taas: _____
 _____ Timbang: _____ BP: _____

Panuto: Punan ang kolum ng mga kinain at ininom mo sa nakalipas na 3 araw gayon din ang mga kaukulang gawain. Magsimula sa pinakahuling araw (kahapon), ang araw bago ang kahapon (makalawa), at panghuli, sa 3 araw na nakalipas.

Petsa: _____

Oras	Uri ng Pagkain <i>(hal. saging, pandesal, kape, juice, sabaw)</i>	Dami/Halaga/Serving <i>(hal. tasa, piraso, hiwa, kutsarita, lata, bote)</i>	Saan/Lugar <i>(hal. Bahay, restoran, kantina, kapihan, fastfood)</i>	Paraan ng Paghahanda <i>(hal. inilaga, hinurno, pinasingawan, ipinirito, sariwa)</i>	Pagkagutom 0-5 <i>(0-di gutom, 5-sobrang gutom)</i>	Pagkabusog 0-5 <i>(0-di busog, 5-sobrang busog)</i>	Ispesipiko ng mga ginawa <i>(hal. pagpa-rehab, naglaba, paglimis ng bahay, panood ng TV)</i>	Tagal/Haba <i>(hal. 30 minuto, 1 oras)</i>
Almusal								
Meryenda sa umaga								
Tanghalian								
Meryenda sa hapon								
Hapunan								
Meryenda bago matulog								

Appendix F

The Mini-Mental State Exam

The Mini-Mental State Exam

Pasyente _____ Tagasiyasat _____ Petsa _____

Pinakamataas Iskor

- Pag-aangkop/Oryentasyon**
- 5 () Ano ang (taon) (panahon) (petsa) (araw) (buwan)?
- 5 () Nasaan tayo (estado) (bansa) (bayan) (ospital) (palapag)?
- Rehistrasyon**
- 3 () Magbanggit ng 3 bagay. 1 segundo para banggitin ang bawat isa.
- Pagkatapos, itanong sa pasyente ang 3 binanggit mo. Magbigay ng 1 puntos para sa bawat tamang sagot. Pagkatapos, ulitin hanggang sa matutunan lahat ng pasyente. Bilangin ang pagsubok at irekord. Pagsubok _____
- Pagbibigay-pansin at Pagkakalkula**
- 5 () Serye ng 7. 1 puntos para sa bawat tamang sagot. Tumigil pagkatapos ng 5 sagot. Alternatibong baybayin ng pabalik ang "world".
- Pag-alalang muli/recall**
- 3 () Itanong ang 3 bagay na inulit sa itaas. Magbigay ng 1 puntos para sa bawat tamang sagot.
- Wika**
- 2 () Magbanggit ng lapis at orasan.
- 1 () Ulitin ang sumusunod "No ifs, and, or buts" (Walang paano kung, at, o pero)
- 3 () Sundin ang 3-yugtong utos:
"Kumuha ng papel, itupi sa gitna, at ilapag sa sahig."
- 1 () Basahin at sundin ang sumusunod: IPIKIT ANG IYONG MGA MATA
- 1 () Sumulat ng pangungusap.
- 1 () Kopyahin ang ipinakitang disenyo.

_____ Kabuuang Iskor

Tantiyahin ang antas ng kamalayan sa iskala _____

Listo Antok na antok Kawalan ng pandamdad Koma

Appendix G The Barthel Index

THE BARTHEL INDEX

Patient Name: _____

Rater Name: _____

Date: _____

Activity	Score
FEEDING 0 = unable 5 = needs help cutting, spreading butter, etc., or requires modified diet 10 = independent	_____
BATHING 0 = dependent 5 = independent (or in shower)	_____
GROOMING 0 = needs to help with personal care 5 = independent face/hair/teeth/shaving (implements provided)	_____
DRESSING 0 = dependent 5 = needs help but can do about half unaided 10 = independent (including buttons, zips, laces, etc.)	_____
BOWELS 0 = incontinent (or needs to be given enemas) 5 = occasional accident 10 = continent	_____
BLADDER 0 = incontinent, or catheterized and unable to manage alone 5 = occasional accident 10 = continent	_____
TOILET USE 0 = dependent 5 = needs some help, but can do something alone 10 = independent (on and off, dressing, wiping)	_____
TRANSFERS (BED TO CHAIR AND BACK) 0 = unable, no sitting balance 5 = major help (one or two people, physical), can sit 10 = minor help (verbal or physical) 15 = independent	_____
MOBILITY (ON LEVEL SURFACES) 0 = immobile or < 50 yards 5 = wheelchair independent, including corners, > 50 yards 10 = walks with help of one person (verbal or physical) > 50 yards 15 = independent (but may use any aid; for example, stick) > 50 yards	_____
STAIRS 0 = unable 5 = needs help (verbal, physical, carrying aid) 10 = independent	_____
TOTAL (0-100): _____	

Appendix H Intervention Protocol

PHASES	TIMING	ACTIVITIES	EQUIPMENT/ MATERIALS	RATIONALE
Pre-Assessment	<p>Week 0</p> <p>0-5 days prior to Implementation</p> <p>Time Needed: 1 week</p>	<p>Introduction of study to the unit head/Chief Operations Officer/ Operations Group Head/Medical Director/President.</p> <p>Endorsement of investigator to rehabilitation center head and supervisor.</p>	<p>Permission Letter</p> <p>Study Protocol/Research Description</p> <p>Pre-evaluation: Barthel's Index Three-day diet recall</p>	<p>In conducting a study, administrative authorization is required in institutional or organizational settings access to clients, members, personnel, or records (Polit et al, 2003).</p> <p>It may be valuable to have the study endorsed or acknowledged by a person, group or organization that has prospective subject's confidence and to communicate this to them (Polit et al, 2003).</p>
Phase 1 Assessment	<p>Week 1 Day 1</p> <p>Time Needed: 10-15 min per form</p>	<p>Identification of potential subjects based on inclusion criteria from the rehabilitation center's database.</p> <p>Arrange an appointment for interested participants thru text, call, email, face-to-face.</p> <p>Introduction of self to the patient.</p>	<p>Pencil/Pen</p> <p>Pre-test Forms: Patient Profile WHOQOL-BREF (World Health Organization's Quality of Life-Bref or Short version) form</p>	<p>Enhances control over sample composition and over extraneous variables and identifies eligible candidates (Polit et al, 2003).</p> <p>Provides anticipatory resources for the patient and family (Newfields et al., 2007)</p> <p>Builds rapport with the patient. (Newfield, 2007).</p> <p>The researcher should provide full disclosure of the nature of the study,</p>

PHASES	TIMING	ACTIVITIES	EQUIPMENT/ MATERIALS	RATIONALE
		<p>Explain the guidelines of the health promotion program.</p> <p>Assure confidentiality of information.</p> <p>Secure the consent.</p> <p>Ask patient to answer questionnaires.</p> <p>Set the schedule for teaching sessions.</p>		<p>the subject's right to refuse, and the likely risks and benefits that would be incurred by the study as part of the research process (De Laune, 2002).</p> <p>The researcher must safeguard the rights of the research participants and should act as an advocate for client's rights during the process (De Laune, 2002).</p> <p>Part of protecting human rights in research is obtaining informed consent. In signing the consent, the person understands the reason of the proposed intervention and agrees to the treatment by signing the form (Burns & Grove, 2000).</p> <p>Provides baseline data of the dependent variable and the demographic data of the respondents.</p> <p>Provides time for future planning.</p>

PHASES	TIMING	ACTIVITIES	EQUIPMENT/ MATERIALS	RATIONALE
<p>Phase 2 Implementation</p>	<p>Week 1-4</p> <p>Day 2-Day11</p> <p>Time Needed: 60 min. per session</p>	<p>Introduce self to patients.</p> <p>Ask patients to introduce self and address the client by preferred name at each contact. Explain the program's flow of activities.</p> <p>Promote consistency in carrying out the intervention (eg. Same nurse, as near same routine as possible).</p> <p>Provide calm, nonthreatening environment. Orient to room and location of rest room.</p> <p>Emphasize to the patients that the program to be given is within the scope of nursing practice only (laboratory tests, rehabilitation therapy is provided by other healthcare professionals</p>	<p>Laptop, projector, microphone BP apparatus, stethoscope, sphygmomano meter, wrist watch with seconds, hand-outs</p>	<p>Provides sense of the familiar and promotes comfort for the client to identify nurse (Newfield, 2007). Reinforces sense of self and decreases anxiety (Newfield, 2007). Orients the participant to the program flow. Promotes the client's sense of control (Newfield, 2007).</p> <p>Decreases unessential stimuli. Facilitates the development of a trusting relationship (Newfield, 2007).</p> <p>Provides basic safety measures. Maintains consistency of environment and facilitates the patient's comfort and decreases anxiety (Newfield, 2007).</p> <p>Clarifies limitations of the study and reinforces the nurse's role, which includes client educator, caregiver, ongoing assessment, coordination and collaboration with other health care providers, maintaining client safety (De Laune, 2002).</p> <p>Assures stable physiologic measures. Provide baseline knowledge of physiologic status.</p>

PHASES	TIMING	ACTIVITIES	EQUIPMENT/ MATERIALS	RATIONALE
		<p>and will not be included in the program).</p> <p>Measures patient's hemodynamic/physiologic parameters (BP, HR, MAP, Weight).</p> <p>Ask patient if he/she has any needs. Assist in meeting patient's physical needs.</p> <p>Provide Information about: Physical Exercise</p>		<p>To seek appropriate assistance as need arises.</p> <p>BP remains the cornerstone of prevention of recurrent stroke (Furie et al., 2011; Rashid et al., 2003; cited by Kronish et al., 2014)</p> <p>It has been suggested that stroke might preferentially be predicted by mean arterial pressure (Verdechia P et al., cited in Schillaci).</p> <p>Assesses concerns prior to the intervention. Enables client to identify barriers to participating in desired activities (Doenges et al., 2006).</p> <p>Promotes maintenance of muscle tone and organ function for overall sense of well-being (Doenges et al. 2006). Client teaching should include emphasizing the need for incorporating exercise into one's lifestyle for physiological benefits (DeLaune et al., 2002) Continuous or accumulated aerobic training for 20 to 60 minutes daily, three to seven days a week is advised for secondary stroke prevention (Stroke</p>

PHASES	TIMING	ACTIVITIES	EQUIPMENT/ MATERIALS	RATIONALE
		<p data-bbox="699 904 810 936">Nutrition</p> <p data-bbox="699 1211 890 1375">Psychological Stroke Awareness: Warning signs of Stroke</p> <p data-bbox="699 1453 842 1518">Relaxation Technique</p> <p data-bbox="699 1890 879 2020">Social Relationships Focus Group Discussion</p>		<p data-bbox="1173 264 1422 329">Society of the Philippines 4th Ed).</p> <p data-bbox="1173 365 1453 629">Assists the patient in maintaining a good nutritional-metabolic status facilitates health promotion and illness prevention (Newfield et al., 2007).</p> <p data-bbox="1173 667 1449 931">Knowledge of disease process and expectations can facilitate adherence to prescribed treatment regimen (Doenges et al., 2006)</p> <p data-bbox="1173 969 1449 1402">Relaxation techniques provide an increased sense of control, reduce stress and anxiety, promote active involvement, elevate mood, and raise the pain threshold (McGuire, Sheidler, &Polomano, 2000, cited by Carpenito- Moyet, 2010).</p> <p data-bbox="1173 1406 1461 1671">Provides knowledge base and encourages participation in decision making. Helps patient to see that he or she is not alone (Newfield et al., 2007).</p> <p data-bbox="1173 1709 1449 1906">Provides information on available healthcare services, and government and non-government institutions.</p> <p data-bbox="1173 1944 1453 2009">Conveys message of concern.</p>

PHASES	TIMING	ACTIVITIES	EQUIPMENT/ MATERIALS	RATIONALE
		<p>Environment Support and services</p> <p>Listen to/active listen client's reports and comments.</p> <p>Encourage patient and family to ask questions or the patient to interact with others.</p> <p>Answer questions using simple/layman's terms and within the scope of nursing.</p> <p>Provide material in multiple formats (e.g., audio-visuals, pamphlets, hands on demonstration)</p>		<p>Helps reduce anxiety and offers clues to related issues (Newfield et al., 2007).</p> <p>Facilitates understanding.</p> <p>Using multiple senses to stimulate learning/retention of information. Provides resources for review (Doenges et al., 2006)</p>
<p>Phase 3 Evaluation</p>	<p>Week 4</p> <p>Day 12</p> <p>Time Needed: 10-15 minutes</p>	<p>Ask patient to answer questionnaires.</p> <p>Measures patient's hemodynamic and physiologic parameters</p>	<p>Pencil/Pen</p> <p>WHOQOL-BREF</p> <p>BP apparatus, stethoscope, wrist watch with seconds.</p>	<p>Provides post-intervention data on the dependent variable</p> <p>Evaluates physiologic parameters post intervention.</p>

PHASES	TIMING	ACTIVITIES	EQUIPMENT/ MATERIALS	RATIONALE
		(BP, HR, MAP, Weight).		

APPENDIX I

Instructional Design

Program: Supportive-Educative Program: Survive Stroke

Description:

This program is designed to provide necessary information, support and practical ideas to assist stroke patients to understand and manage their health, to develop new skills and knowledge to help stroke survivors live well after stroke. This program is considered to be important in secondary stroke prevention. Information on self-care management is covered in this program which includes: physical activity, nutrition, relaxation techniques, safety and support.

Purpose:

This Survive Stroke program aims to help people live well after stroke by providing a supportive-education program administered by a nurse.

Setting: Barangay hall, Diabetes Care Center,

Participants: Research Assistants-Registered nurses (preferably ManilaMed nurses), post-rehab stroke patients

Resources:

Research Assistants

Overhead projector, sound system, brochure/hand outs, snacks

References: Master Stroke Fact sheet (2014); Bartholomew LK, Kok G, Gottlieb NH,

Fernandez ME (2011) Planning Health Promotion Programs: An Intervention Approach 3rd Ed;

National Stroke Association (2010) Hope: The Stroke Recovery Guide

Professional Responsibility:

To provide a systematic discussion of important concepts related to stroke care for secondary prevention

To integrate previous experiences on patient care and knowledge from available resources in providing information

To correlate the discussed concepts within the setting of ManilaMed hospital

Conditions	CONCEPTS/ Competencies	Instructional Activities	Instructional Function	Evaluation Methods/ Tools
Given relevant information	<p>DAY 1 to 4</p> <p>Overview: This section discusses the importance of physical activity and will demonstrate exercises recommended for mildly affected* post-stroke patients. This section will also discuss healthy eating.</p> <p>*Mildly affected: May have obvious stiffness or muscle</p>			<p>A group activity and a short evaluation quiz at the end of the session</p> <p>Return demonstration</p>

	<p>spasms but generally have some ability to control movements.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <p>To discuss the benefits of exercise</p> <p>To demonstrate different types of exercises for those mildly affected by stroke:</p> <p>Strengthen muscles that stabilize shoulder</p> <p>Strengthen shoulder muscles as well as those which straighten the elbow</p> <p>Strengthen the muscles which straighten the elbow</p> <p>Improve hip control</p> <p>Enhance hip and knee control</p> <p>Improve control of knee motions for walking</p> <p>Improve weight shift and control for proper walking technique</p> <p>Improve balance, weight shift and control necessary for walking</p> <p>Stimulate proper weight shift while strengthening hip and pelvis muscles</p> <p>To demonstrate pulse monitoring.</p> <p>To discuss nutrition that will help manage your weight and blood pressure.</p> <p>Importance of ideal body weight</p> <p>Tips for eating healthy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -low salt -low fat -low calories 	<p>Demonstrate how to perform the exercises. Monitor pulse before and after exercise and compute for the normal range.</p> <p>Demonstrate how to make a food diary.</p>	<p>Transmitting information; demonstrating behaviors to be learned; allowing the participants to practice the exercise.</p> <p>Transmitting information; demonstrating behaviors to be learned; allowing the participants to practice the behavior</p>	<p>Self-monitoring sheet</p>
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	Sample meal plan			
Given relevant information	<p>DAY 5 to 6</p> <p>Overview: This section recognizes the victims of stroke as survivors. It begins with the explanation of stroke and discusses steps on what they can do after stroke. This section discusses ways to prevent recurrence of stroke through modification of risk factors and relaxation techniques.</p> <p>Objectives: To briefly define Stroke Basic Pathophysiology Warning Signs and Symptoms To define secondary stroke prevention self-advocacy To discuss risk factors as follows: Controllable Uncontrollable</p>	<p>Provide information to help understand what has happened and what to do next Provide ways of secondary prevention (eg. smoking cessation, diet, exercise) Encourage patients to seek out and listen to not be afraid to ask for help when needed from members of healthcare team and other stroke survivors as well</p> <p>Discuss the two types of risk factors Enumerate the controllable/unc controllable risk factors Discuss the basic signs of stroke for early detection and prompt treatment</p>	<p>Providing a frame of reference; providing a reason to learn; shaping one's attitudes</p> <p>Transmitting information; providing a reason to learn</p> <p>Transmitting information; providing a reason to learn</p>	<p>Short evaluation quiz at the end the session</p> <p>Short evaluation quiz at the end the session</p>

			<p>Transmitting information; providing a reason to learn</p> <p>Providing a frame of reference; providing a reason to learn; shaping one's attitudes</p> <p>Transmitting information; providing a reason to learn</p>	
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<p>Given relevant information</p>	<p>Day 7 to 8</p> <p>Overview: This section covers the different approaches to address the psychosocial needs of post-stroke patients. It begins with discussion on the common behavioral changes post stroke. This culminates with a group activity utilizing imagery as a coping strategy.</p> <p>Objectives: To explain behavior, emotions and thinking changes following stroke. Depression Apathy Memory Loss Concentration/Perception Problems One-sided Neglect Emotional Lability</p> <p>To participate in the group activity on biobehavioral intervention: Imagery</p>	<p>Provide a general idea about the patient's behavioral changes post stroke Provide a concise definition of human needs Encourage participants to utilize imagery as a relaxation technique Provide handouts</p>	<p>Providing a frame of reference; providing a reason to learn</p> <p>Transmitting information; shaping one's attitude</p>	<p>Short evaluation quiz at the end the session</p> <p>Demonstration</p>
<p>Given relevant information</p>	<p>Day 9 to 10</p> <p>Overview: This section covers the different factors in the environment that may affect stroke survivor's daily living.</p> <p>Objectives: To discuss safety Home modifications Assistive devices</p>		<p>Transmitting information; shaping one's attitude</p> <p>Transmitting information;</p>	

	To discuss available services in the community		shaping one's attitude	
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Survive Stroke Program Information Flyer

WHAT IS THE *SURVIVE STROKE* PROGRAM?

Survive Stroke is a supportive-educative program study conducted for stroke survivors that aims to help people live well after stroke by combining exercise, nutrition, education and support from health professionals.

WHY ATTEND *SURVIVE STROKE*?

There are a number of risk factors for stroke that *can* be controlled. In addition to medical management (like medication) you can help reduce your risk of another stroke by maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Did you know being active, eating healthy food, quitting smoking and limiting alcohol can all help to reduce the risk of stroke?

Survive Stroke will provide you with information, support and practical ideas to help you to understand your medical management and develop or maintain a healthy and active lifestyle.

Survive Stroke will also assist you to understand and manage the effects of your stroke.

The ultimate aim of the program is to give you the skills to be able to manage your own health. You'll have the opportunity to have your questions answered and to develop new skills and knowledge to help you live well after stroke. You'll also be able to meet others in a similar situation.

WHEN AND WHERE IS *SURVIVE STROKE* HELD?

Survive Stroke runs **thrice weekly for a month.**

You will need to come on these days:

- Monday morning
- Wednesday morning
- Friday morning

ARE ANY ASSESSMENTS NEEDED?

You will need to attend one individual appointment, for up to 60 minutes, prior to the

program commencing

This will involve completion of questionnaires and physical assessments to provide information such as 3day diet recall, functional level to make sure that the program is safe and suitable for you.

Medical clearance from your physician will also be required (we will help obtain this for you).

Reassessments will be completed at the end of the program, and then 3 months after, to monitor any changes or progress since attending Survive Stroke.

WHAT ABOUT THE EXERCISE SESSION?

The sessions will be held in the Penthouse Auditorium of ManilaMed.

A nurse will help you in the class.

Exercise sessions will be 60 minutes - but there are breaks!

The exercise session may help to:

Improve your fitness – so you can manage more of the activities you'd like to do

Improve your strength and balance

WHO CAN ATTEND THE PROGRAM?

The program is open to anyone who has had a stroke or TIA and lives in Metro Manila area.

Survive Stroke groups participants need to be able to safely follow exercise instructions; be able to use the toilet independently (or with the help of their carer); understand Tagalog or/and English (as it is not feasible to use interpreters in group education sessions); have intact receptive communication (understand what is being said); have no evidence of major cognitive impairment or dementia.

A support person is encouraged to also attend with you (eg carer or family member). This can be very helpful for support with maintaining lifestyle changes at home. Due to the size of the auditorium room there is only space for one support person per participant.

IS THERE A COST FOR THE PROGRAM?

There is no cost to attend the Survive Stroke program.

A light morning tea will be supplied on Mondays at no charge.

Morning snacks will be available after each session at no charge.

APPENDIX J
Informed Consent Form

In signing this document, I am giving my consent to participate in a Supportive-Educative Program by a student of University of the Philippines Open University, Manila. I understand that I will be a part of a research study that will focus on Quality of Life of Stroke Survivors. This study is not supported by any private or public organization.

I understand that I will participate in a Supportive-Educative Program activity three times a week, for 2 hours in the ManilaMed Penthouse Auditorium with other stroke survivors. I will answer questions about my experience as a stroke patient and will be asked to answer questionnaires in writing. It may take 15 minutes to 30 minutes to complete. I also understand that the researcher may contact me or my significant other for more information in the future.

I understand that I am selected to participate in this study because I am an adult stroke survivor, have finished formal rehabilitation, have submitted a medical consent, and able to follow instructions.

I have been informed that my participation is entirely voluntary and at any time I can refuse to answer or decide to terminate the interview at any point. I have been told that my answer to questions will not be given to anyone else and no reports of this study will ever identify me in any way. I have also been informed that my participation or my refusal to answer questions will have no effect on services that I or any member of my family may receive from health or social services providers.

This study will help develop a better understanding of the experiences of stroke survivors and the services that can be most helpful to stroke victims. However, I will receive no direct benefit as a result of participation.

I understand that the results of this research will be given to me if I ask of them and that Alana Aissa Gem Barias is the person to contact if I have any questions about the study or about my rights as a study participant. Ms. Barias can be reached through these numbers: 09192991882.

Date

Respondent's Signature

Researcher's Signature

APPENDIX K
Research Flow

APPENDIX L
CURRICULUM VITAE

ALANA AISSA GEM B. BARIAS
Mobile number: +639192991882
Telephone number: 085-3419056
E-mail Address: bariasalana@yahoo.com

Career Objectives: To use my skills in the best possible way for achieving the company's goals and to enhance my professional skills through ongoing education and trainings in a dynamic workplace that provides opportunity for professional challenges and growth.

EDUCATION

Masters of Arts in Nursing, Major in Adult Health Nursing

University of the Philippines Open University
Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines
June 2010- December 2021

Bachelor of Science in Nursing

Velez College
F. Ramos Street, Cebu City, Philippines
June 2002-March 2006

NURSING REGISTRATION LICENSES

Registered Nurse

Certifying Body: Philippine Regulations Commission, Philippines
License No: 0425396 Issued: March 12, 2007

Registered Nurse

Certifying Body: State of Vermont Board of Nursing, USA
License No: 0041371 Issued: April 1, 2009

Registered Nurse

Certifying Body: State of New York, USA
License No: 633261-1 Issued: August 9, 2010

Registered Nurse

Certifying Body: Saudi Council for Health Sciences, Saudi Arabia
License No: 09JN0292923 Issued: January 6, 2010

WORK EXPERIENCE

Ambulatory Care Nurse

February 2021-Present
General Surgery Unit/Hematology-Oncology Unit
New York Health and Hospitals-Metropolitan
New York, New York, United States of America

Staff Nurse

January 2020-July 2021
Pulmonary Unit
St. John's Episcopal Hospital
Far Rockaway, Queens
New York, United States of America

Staff Nurse

July 2018-February 2021
Caring Family Nursing and Rehabilitation Center
Far Rockaway, Queens
New York, United States of America

Diabetes Nurse Educator

January 29, 2015 – January 30, 2017
Medical Center Manila (Manila-Med)
UN Avenue, Manila, Philippines

Staff Nurse

Institute of Neurosciences
March 15, 2014 to August 8, 2014
Saint Luke's Medical Center, E Rodriguez
Quezon City, Philippines

Staff Nurse

July 3, 2009 to October 2011
Medical-Surgical, Aesthetic Surgery, Emergency, Pediatrics, OB-GYN
Al- Sahly Early Diagnostic Polyclinic, Al Marwa District, Prince Majed
Jeddah City, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Volunteer Nurse

Medical-Surgical Ward
March to May 2007; January to March 2009
Butuan Doctors Hospital, J.C. Aquino Avenue
Butuan City, Philippines

Clinical Instructor

Hospital (Clinical) and Classroom (Lecture)
June to December 2007
Father Saturnino Urios University
Butuan City, Philippines

NURSING SEMINARS/TRAININGS ATTENDED

Progressive Care Nursing Standards of Practice and Certification Review

March 14-15, 2023

Provided by: New York State Nurse Association

Psychiatric Mental Health Nursing Standards of Practice and Certification Review

March 9-10, 2023

Provided by: New York State Nurse Association

Medical-Surgical Nursing Standards of Practice and Certification Review

March 7-8, 2023

Provided by: New York State Nurse Association

Improving Care Quality and Long-Term Outcomes for Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease

November 16, 2022

Provided by: New York State Nurse Association

Engaging Young Adults and Families in Meningococcal Disease Prevention: An Educational Toolkit

November 16, 2022

Provided by: Prime Education

Clinical Breakthrough in Recurrent Vulvovaginal Candidiasis (RVVC) Managed Care Perspectives

November 2, 2022

Provided by: Prime Education

Promoting Health Equity in Stroke: Transforming Patient Insights Into Change

November 1, 2022

Provided by: Prime Education

The Many Faces of Menopause: A Patient-Centered Approach to Advance Care Vasomotor Symptoms in Menopausal and Postmenopausal Women

November 1, 2022

Provided by: Prime Education

Expert Approaches to VTE Care for Patients and Obesity

November 1, 2022

Provided by: Prime Education

Achieving Treatment Goals in Type 2 Diabetes Through Collaborative Learning: A Toolkit for Clinical Teams

October 28, 2022

Provided by: Prime Education

Pathophysiology of Hypercholesterolemia and Mechanisms of Action of Non-statin Therapies

October 25, 2022
Provided by: Prime Education

Clinical Pathways for Successful HIV Prevention Program

October 25, 2022
Provided by: Prime Education

Pursuing Functional Cure in HBV: What's New?

October 26, 2022
Provided by: Prime Education

Early ART Initiation: Effective Models Across Diverse Patients and Settings

October 24, 2022
Provided by: Prime Education

Promoting Health Equity in Atrial Fibrillation: Real-World Patient Insight and Expert Strategies for Delivering Evidence-Based Care

October 25, 2022
Provided by: Prime Education

Transforming HR+/HER2 Breast Cancer Care: Real-world Patient and Provider Perspectives

October 25, 2022
Provided by: Prime Education

Crisis Prevention and Management

March 9, 2021
Provided by: New York Health and Hospitals

Placement and Care of CVCs

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Handoff Communication

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Ethics

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Back Safety

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Religion and Spirituality

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Cultural and Age Related Competencies

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Disaster Recovery and Emergency Preparedness

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Fire Safety

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Pain Management Responsibilities

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Responsible Use of Social Media

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Regulation Express: Slips, Trips, and Falls

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Computer Security

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Patient Bill of Rights

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Recognizing Abuse

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Hazardous Materials

November 13, 2020
Provided by: St.John's Episcopal Hospital (Relias)

Basic Cardiac Life Support

January 3, 2020
Provided by: American Heart Association, Nationwide Health LLC

Capacity Building in Research Simplifying Research Proposal Development

October 16, 2023
Provided by: Philippine Nurses Association, Manila

22nd National Assembly of Diabetes Educators

November 9, 2016
Provided by: Philippine Center for Diabetes Education Foundation Inc.

Diabetes Education Training

April 27 to May 12, 2015

Provided by: Philippine Association of Diabetes Educators & Association of Diabetes Nurse Educators of the Philippines (PADE-ADNEP)

Caring for the Stroke Survivor

January 23, 2015

Provided by: Philippine Nurses Association, Manila

Primary Stroke

August 1, 2014

Provided by: St. Luke's Medical Center, Quezon City

Bringing Values to the Workplace: Nurses Making A Difference

May 10, 2014

Provided by: Philippine Nurses Association, Manila

Theoretical Base in Advanced Nursing Practice

April 26, 2014

Provided by: Trinity University of Asia

Pressure Ulcer Training

March 26, 2014

Provided by: Nursing Quality Organization (St. Luke's Medical Center)

ABCs of Chemotherapy

March 21, 2014

Provided by: St. Luke's Medical Center, Quezon City

Acute Brain Attack

March 7, 2014

Provided by: Philippine Nurses Association, Manila

Urologic Nursing Care

August 30, 2013

Provided by: St. Luke's Medical Center, Quezon City

Bio-Safety Emergency Preparedness and Disaster Control Team

August 16, 2013

Provided by: St. Luke's Medical Center, Quezon City

Guided Clinical Practicum

June 17, 2013- July 12, 2013

Provided by: St. Luke's Medical Center, Quezon City

Care Processes

April 22, 2013- May 31, 2013

Provided by: St. Luke's Medical Center, Quezon City

Quality and Safety Standards

March 6, 2013- April 4, 2013
Provided by: St. Luke's Medical Center, Quezon City

Basic Intravenous Therapy Training Program

November 8-10, 2012
Provided by: Medical Center Manila, Metro Manila

Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS) Course

January 25-27, 2012
Provided by: NLE Central

Cancer Chemotherapy

October 28, 2011
Provided by Philippine Nurses Association

Basic Cardiac Life Support Provider

November 9, 2009
Provided by: Saudi German Hospitals Group

Clinical Instructor's Training

May 21-26, 2007
Provided by: Agusan del Norte, Provincial Hospital

SUMMARY OF ACHIEVEMENTS

Nursing Licensure Examination Rating of *81.20%*
Taken on December 2006, Cebu City

HERO Award (Hospital Employee Reaching Out Award)
July 14, 2014
Institute of Neuroscience, St. Luke's Medical Center

International English Language Testing System (IELTS)
July 2015
Overall Band Score: 8.0
Listening: 8.5 Reading: 8.0 Writing: 7.0 Speaking: 7.5

Toastmasters International
November 17, 2016
Competent Communicator Norm

OTHER CERTIFICATES/SEMINARS

Speaker

Beat Diabetes Through Healthy Lifestyle
September 26, 2016
Provided by: Rotary International (San Juan West)

Speaker

World Diabetes Day: "Eyes on Diabetes"

November 24, 2016
Provided by: Medical Center Manila (Manila-Med)

Facilitator

National Diabetes Awareness Week: “Be Bold, Be Brave: Beat Diabetes”
July 21, 2016
Provided by: Medical Center Manila (Manila-Med)

Facilitator

Insulin Administration and Insulin Types
May 11, 2016
Provided by: Medical Center Manila (Manila-Med)

Resource Person

World Diabetes Awareness Day
November 10, 2015
Provided by: Medical Center Manila (Manila-Med)

Resource Person

Workshop on Diabetes Prevention and Management Updates
July 31, 2015
Provided by: Medical Center Manila (Manila-Med)

Resource Person/Process Facilitator

Workshop on Development of DOH Nurse Certification Program Assessment
Rubrics for Geriatric Nursing
May 20-22, 2015
Provided by: Department of Health, Health Human Resource Development Bureau

Facilitator

Workshop on Development of DOH Nurse Certification Program Assessment
Rubrics for Maternal and Child Nursing
March 17-19, 2015
Provided by: Department of Health, Health Human Resource Development Bureau

Facilitator

Workshop on Development of DOH Nurse Certification Program Assessment
Rubrics for Infectious Disease
March 3-5, 2015
Provided by: Department of Health, Health Human Resource Development Bureau

Facilitator

Workshop on Development of DOH Nurse Certification Program Assessment
Rubrics for Orthopedic and Rehabilitation Nursing
October 22-24, 2014
Provided by: Department of Health, Health Human Resource Development Bureau

Facilitator

Workshop on Development of DOH Nurse Certification Program Assessment
Rubrics for Renal Nursing

October 7-10, 2014

Provided by: Department of Health, Health Human Resource Development Bureau

National Institute of Health Stroke Scale-English Group A-V3 Completion

March 31, 2014

Provided by: Training Campus- NIHSS-English (St. Luke's Medical Center)

A(H1N1) Disseminator

June 24, 2009

Provided by: The Philippine National Red Cross

PROFESSIONAL AFFILIATIONS

Philippine Nurses Association

Member 2007- Present

New York State Nurses Association

Member 2021- Present

TALENTS

Language Spoken: Tagalog, English, Visayan, Arabic, French

Computer Skills: Microsoft Word, Excel, PowerPoint

Others: Sing, Dance, Sketch, Paint, Calligraphy

REFERENCES

Queenie R. Ridulme, BSN, RN, MAN

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Management and Development Studie/ Former
Program Chair - Master of Arts in Nursing

University of the Philippines-Open University, Los Baños, Philippines

Contact: manpc@upou.edu.ph / queenieridulme@upou.edu.ph

Werlina Subervi, BSN, RN, AMB-BC

Head Nurse, Ambulatory Care - General Surgery Unit

New York Health and Hospitals-Metropolitan, New York, USA

Contact: wmsrn87@yahoo.com

Nora Gapasin, BSN, RN

Head Nurse, Ambulatory Care – Hematology-Oncology Unit/Infusion Center

New York Health and Hospitals-Metropolitan, New York, USA

Contact: nora.gapasin@nychhc.org